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A faunistic review of darkling beetles (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae; excluding Alleculinae) of Armenia and partly the Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic of Azerbaijan with new records and taxonomic notes

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Abstract. The faunistic review of Tenebrionidae (excluding Alleculinae) from Armenia is presented. The work is based on long-term collections of one of the authors and materials from museum collections, deposited in Yerevan (the most of material), St Petersburg and Budapest. In total, 123 species of Tenebrionidae, excluding Alleculinae are reliably known from Armenia and confirmed by material. The checklist contains data on specimens (number of specimens and geographic labels) deposited in the museums. Sometimes we refer to reliable sources with the indicated material. Thus, all data have been verified, and the habitat of each species has been confirmed by collection material. The following seven species are recorded from Armenia for the first time: *Hedyphanes laticollis* Fischer von Waldheim in Ménériés, 1832 (the first confirmed record), *Palorus orientalis* Fleischer, 1900, *Tenebrio angustus* Zoufal, 1892, *Pentaphyllus testaceus* (Hellwig, 1792), *Corticeus longulus* (Gyllenhal, 1827), *C. suberis* (Lucas, 1846), *Myrmexchixenus picinus* (Aubé, 1850). Four latter species are also new for Transcaucasia. The following four species are recorded for Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic (Azerbaijan) for the first time: *Aspidocephalus desertus* Motschulsky, 1839, *Gonocephalum setulosum* (Faldermann, 1837), *Palorus ratzeburgii* (Wissmann, 1848), *Cnemeplatia atropos* A. Costa, 1847. The following 14 species are excluded from the faunistic list of Armenia because they are not confirmed by collection material: *Cnemeplatia atropos*, *Philhammus cribratellus* Reitter, 1901, *Lachnogyia squamosa* Ménériés, 1848, *Leptodes lederi* Reitter, 1889, *Sternoplax armeniaca* (Faldermann, 1837), *Lagria atripes* Mulsant et Guillebeau, 1855, *Blaps scabriuscula scabriuscula* Ménériés, 1832, *Neopachypterus serrulatus* (Reitter, 1904), *Opatrum verrucosum* Germar, 1817, *Penthicus pinguis pinguis* Faldermann, 1836, *Sclerum carinatum* Baudi di Selve, 1875, *Leichenium canaliculatum canaliculatum* (Fabricius, 1798), *Helops caeruleus stevenii* Krynicki, 1834, *Ulloma culinaris* (Linnaeus, 1758).

In addition, we presented corrections (we excluded 15 species as a result of synonymy or incorrect distribution data) to the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, which were made in previous works (before the date of publication in 2020) but omitted in this catalogue. A new synonymy is proposed: *Cyphostethe semenovi* Bogatchev, 1947 = *Cyphostethe jelineki* Merkl, 1991, **syn. n.** The species *Pimelia persica* Faldermann, 1837 is transferred from the nominotypical subgenus to the subgenus *Chaetotoma* Motschulsky, 1860. Two species, *Tenebrio angustus* and *Palorus orientalis*, are synantropic invaders in Armenia.

Key words: tenebrionid beetles, Transcaucasia, fauna, new records, new synonymy, check-list.

Фаунистический обзор жуков-чернотелок (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae; кроме Alleculinae) Армении и частично Нахичеванской Автономной Республики Азербайджана с новыми находками и таксономическими замечаниями

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Резюме. Представлен фаунистический обзор жуков-чернотелок (Tenebrionidae, за исключением Alleculinae) Армении. Работа основана на многолетних сборах одного из авторов и материалах из музейных собраний, хранящихся в Ереване (большая часть материала), Санкт-Петербурге и Будапеште. Всего 123 вида Tenebrionidae (без Alleculinae) достоверно зарегистрировано в Армении. Список видов содержит данные о количестве экземпляров и географические этикетки. В ряде случаев предоставлены ссылки на достоверные источники, содержащие сведения о собранных экземплярах. Таким образом, все таксоны верифицированы, а обитание каждого вида в стране подтверждено коллекционным материалом. Семь видов новые для фауны Армении: *Hedyphanes laticollis* Fischer von Waldheim in Ménériés, 1832 (первая подтвержденная находка), *Palorus orientalis* Fleischer, 1900, *Tenebrio angustus* Zoufal, 1892, *Pentaphyllus testaceus* (Hellwig, 1792), *Corticeus longulus* (Gyllenhal, 1827), *Corticeus suberis* (Lucas, 1846), *Myrmexchixenus picinus* (Aubé, 1850). Четыре последних вида также новые для Закавказья. Виды, новые для Нахичеванской Автономной Республики Азербайджана: *Aspidocephalus desertus* Motschulsky, 1839, *Gonocephalum setulosum* (Faldermann, 1837), *Palorus ratzeburgii* (Wissmann, 1848), *Cnemeplatia atropos* A. Costa, 1847. Следующие 14 видов исключены из фаунистического списка Армении, так как их указания не подтверждены коллекционным материалом: *Cnemeplatia*

atropos, *Philhammus cribratellus* Reitter, 1901, *Lachnogyia squamosa* Ménériés, 1848, *Leptodes lederi* Reitter, 1889, *Sternoplax armeniaca* (Faldermann, 1837), *Lagria atripes* Mulsant et Guillebeau, 1855, *Blaps scabriuscula scabriuscula* Ménériés, 1832, *Neopachypterus serrulatus* (Reitter, 1904), *Opatrum verrucosum* Germar, 1817, *Penthicus pinguis pinguis* Faldermann, 1836, *Sclerum carinatum* Baudi di Selve, 1875, *Leichenium canaliculatum canaliculatum* (Fabricius, 1798), *Helops caeruleus stevenii* Krynicki, 1834, *Uloma culinaris* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Кроме того, предложены исправления (исключено 15 видов в результате синонимии или неверных данных о распространении) в каталог жесткокрылых Палеарктики, которые были опубликованы ранее, но пропущены в последней редакции каталога.

Установлен новый синоним: *Cyphostethe semenovi* Bogatchev, 1947 = *Cyphostethe jelineki* Merkl, 1991, **syn. n.** Вид *Pimelia persica* Faldermann, 1837 перенесен из номинотипичного подрода в подрод *Chaetotoma* Motschulsky, 1860. Два вида, *Tenebrio angustus* и *Palorus orientalis*, рассматриваются нами как синантропные вселенцы на территории Армении.

Ключевые слова: жуки-чернотелки, Закавказье, фауна, новые находки, новая синонимия, чек-лист.

Introduction

The fauna of darkling beetles of Armenia is well studied, especially after summarized books of Iablokoff-Khznorian [1983] and Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011]. However, this mountain country contains many faunistic surprises. Therefore, when material accumulates, it becomes necessary to update previously published information. In addition, many faunistic records (especially old ones) for Armenia are erroneous and based on specimens labelled as “Armenia” or an analogue in other languages. Since the borders of the country were permanently changing, many of these records are no longer relevant or were initially erroneous. The majority of these erroneous records were published and discussed [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011] but were not considered in the latest edition of the Palaearctic catalogue [Catalogue..., 2020].

An extensive bibliography for each species was previously published for Alleculinae prior to 1983 [Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1983] and for the rest of Tenebrionidae prior to 2011 [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011], therefore we do not repeat this information here. Nevertheless, it is necessary to mention several taxonomic works on darkling beetles of Armenia, published after 2011. Nabozhenko and coauthors published revisions of the genera *Cylindrinotus* Faldermann, 1837 [Nabozhenko, 2015] and *Odocnemis* Allard, 1876 (Tenebrioninae: Helopini) [Nabozhenko, Keskin, 2016] with many localities in Armenia and new species, a taxonomic revision of *Ceratanisus* Gemminger, 1870 with the description of two new species from Armenia [Nabozhenko et al., 2016a], new records and taxonomy of the genera *Blaps* Fabricius, 1775 [I. Chigray, Nabozhenko, 2016], *Scaurus* Fabricius, 1775 [Nabozhenko et al., 2018] and *Calyptopsis* Solier, 1835 [S. Chigray et al., 2018]. Finally, the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera [Iwan et al., 2020] has been recently published by an international team of authors. A little later, Schawaller [2020] published some synonyms and faunistic records in the genus *Laena* Dejean, 1821 from Armenia. In total, 187 species and subspecies of Tenebrionidae are listed in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020]. However, due to the numerous erroneously recorded taxa, synonyms as available species and the absence of really distributed in Armenia species, this number cannot be considered.

Below we present labelled data on the species of Tenebrionidae of Armenia, excluding the subfamily

Alleculinae, which was revised early in detail [Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1983]. We also added corrections to the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020].

Material and methods

The study is based mainly on material deposited in the Scientific Center of Zoology and Hydroecology, National Academy of Sciences of Armenia. We do not give an acronym for this institution for each species in the “Material” sections, but we use acronyms for following museums in several cases (acronyms are given in the “Material” section): ZIN – Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (St Petersburg, Russia); HNHM – Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary).

Label data is given in English, with current names that can be found on commonly used network resources (Google Earth, Google Maps, Geonames, etc.). The Dictionary of Toponyms of Armenia and Adjacent Regions [Hakobyan et al., 1986, 1988, 1991, 1998, 2001] was used for the decipherment of historical names. We use current names for each locality, even in case of old names on labels. The material is distributed according to the modern administrative division by regions (marzes) of the Republic of Armenia, including Yerevan as a separate region, in order from northwest to southeast. The coordinates of localities obtained in the fieldwork using GPS devices are given. In some cases, coordinates are also given for old materials when the authors know the exact places of collection (from expedition diaries, memoirs, etc.).

The general distribution of each species is presented in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020], therefore we give it only for Armenia or for neighbouring countries in case of necessity to clarify the range. Thus, the “Distribution” in the checklist should be understood as distribution in Armenia. Given the volume of the material presented below, we do not mark the sex of specimens, except for the taxa with well expressed sexual dimorphism because it is not a taxonomic review. In this case, localities are more important. We don't add names of nominotypical subgenera in brackets.

We use the order of subfamilies, tribes and subtribes according to Bouchard et al. [2021]. Genera and species within tribes/subtribes are given in alphabetical order. We use 1761 (not 1760) for taxa, described by Linnaeus in the second edition of “Fauna Svecica” [Zilli, 2021].

Check-list of Tenebrionidae of Armenia (without Alleculinae)

Subfamily Pimeliinae Latreille, 1802

Tribe Adesmiini Lacordaire, 1859

Adesmia maillei Solier, 1835

Material. Armavir Prov.: Sardarapat environs, 3♂, 2♀, 12.09.1924, 3♂, 3♀, 3.10.1924, 3♂, 12.11.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 8♂, 4♀, Parakar environs, 23–24.09.1925 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 15♂, 8♀, same locality, 7.10.1928 (L. Bekosipov); 10♂, 5♀, Lukashin, 7.10.1928 (unknown collector); 3♂, Nalbandyan, 12.11.1930 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); steppe near Echmiadzin, 3♂, 20.04.1930, 1♀, 12.11.1930, 7♂, 3♀, 19–20.10.1935, 1♀, 6.12.1935 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1♂, Arazap environs, “Vordan Karmir” Sanctuary, 40.0630°N / 44.1259°E, 850 m, 28.09.2018 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Baghramyan environs, 40.1779°N / 43.8389°E, 1070 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 11♂, 5♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♂, 20.09.1907, 1♀, 24.09.1910, 3♂, 1♀, 4–16.10.1910, 1♂, 12.10.1912 (V. Dobrowljanskiy); 2♂, 1♀, same locality, 13.09.1927 (G. Ismailov); 1♂, Yerevan environs, 11.07.1925 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 7♂, 1♀, Nubarashen, 19.09.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, Masis, 31.08.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Ararat town environs, 23–26.10.1932 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1♂, Vedi, 1.09.1983 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, W environs of Paruyr Sevak, 39.7581°N / 44.8934°E, 1120 m, 1.08.2002; “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1♀, 22.10.1986, 1♂, 20.07.2014 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., SE environs of Meghri, abandoned railway station, 17.08.1996 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. The species was listed for Ararat valley [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for southern Armenia.

Tribe Akidini Billberg, 1820

Cyphogenia (Lechriomus) lucifuga (Adams, 1817)

Material. Lori Prov.: 1 ex., Ardvi, 14.08.1937 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Talin, 2.07.1928 (O. Amirdjanian); 2 ex., Ashtarak, 15.06.1996 (A. Malkhasyan).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 10.07.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., N environs of Geghadir, 20.08.1997 (A. Malkhasyan);

Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Armavir vill. (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Metsamor Historical-Archeological Museum-Reserve, 13.04.2021 (M. Arakelyan); 1 ex., steppe near Echmiadzin, 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1 ex., 16.04.1907, 2 ex., 10.04.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskiy); same locality, 1 ex., 10.05.1924, 2 ex., 26.05.1924, 1 ex., 7.07.1924 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 1 ex., 6.05.1951, 1 ex., 2.08.1952, 1 ex., 20.09.1974 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Yerevan environs, 17.07.1928 (M. Makarian); 1 ex., Yerevan, gardens, 10–11.05.1933 (Asisian); 1 ex., Jrvezh, 4.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 2 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 28–29.06.1933 (Paramonov); 3 ex., same locality, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, at light, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan, M. Mazmanyanyan); 1 ex., Armash environs, 10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Armash, 39.7671°N / 44.8105°E, 840 m, 14.05.2021 (T. Ghrejyan).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: Areni environs, 14.06.1977 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Everywhere in Armenia.

Tribe Boromorphini Skopin, 1978

Boromorphus armeniacus Reitter, 1889

Material. Yerevan: Nubarashen, 2 ex., 3.04.1951, 6 ex., 3.03.1952, 2 ex., 3.05.1952, 1 ex., 3.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species was known from Meghri (Syunik Province) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for central Armenia.

Boromorphus opaculus Reitter, 1887

Notes. The species was recorded for Armenia [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011] based on specimens from Yerevan and Echmiadzin deposited in ZIN.

Tribe Ceratanisini Gebien, 1937

Ceratanisus transcaucasicus Nabozhenko, Ferrer, Kalashian et Abdurakhmanov, 2016

See type material in Nabozhenko et al. [2016a].

Ceratanisus khnznoriani Nabozhenko, Ferrer, Kalashian et Abdurakhmanov, 2016

See type material in Nabozhenko et al. [2016a].

Material. Syunik Prov.: Meghri environs, 6.06.1993 (M. Kalashian).

Tribe Epitragini Blanchard, 1845

Cyphostethe (Cyphostethoides) semenovi Bogatchev, 1947

= *Cyphostethe jelineki* Merkl, 1991, **syn. n.**

Material. Yerevan: 2 ex., Karmir Blur, 22.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian). Ararat Prov.: 4 ex. (HNHM), Vedi, Gorovan sands, 20.07.1983 (M. Kalashian); 6 ex., “Goravan Sands” Sanctuary, 940 m, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 20.07.1995 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., W environs of Paruyr Sevak, 39.7581°N / 44.8934°E, 1120 m, 23.07.1998 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex. (HNHM), 5 km E Yerashk, 1120 m, 39.75°N / 44.9°E, 23.07.1998 (M. Kalashian); 3 ex., ~6 km ENE Surenavan, 39.8255°N / 44.8383°E, 1480 m, 12–13.07.2007 (M. Kalashian); 6 ex. (HNHM), Surenavan, 19.08.2009 (S. Ilniczky); 2 ex., ~5.5 km E Surenavan, 39.8097°N / 44.8354°E, 1245 m, 18–19.07.2014 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, at light, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan, M. Mazmanyanyan).

Note. The species is included in the Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia [Kalashyan, 2010a]. *Cyphostethe jelineki* was described from Iran [Merkl, 1991] and recorded later for Armenia [Nabozhenko et al., 2016b] after the personal communication of Ottó Merkl, who informed the first author that he has specimens from this country. We examined 11 beetles, determined by O. Merkl as *C. jelineki* and found that he described and interpreted *C. semenovi* as *C. jelineki*. Ottó Merkl misinterpreted *C. semenovi* and based his comparative diagnosis on the characters in Kaszab's key [Kaszab, 1979] and specimens from Central Iran (Kerman) in the HNHM collection, erroneously identified by Kaszab as *C. semenovi*. We did not find two syntypes of *C. semenovi* (described from Bash-Norashen, Nakhichevan, Azerbaijan) in the Institute of Zoology of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan (Baku, Azerbaijan; the majority of darkling beetles in this collection were destroyed by Dermestidae) as well as in Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (Moscow, Russia) and ZIN. Bogatshev published the detailed description of *C. semenovi*, and the characters of his species correspond to those in *C. jelineki* (especially the transverse pronotum with strongly rounded margins). He wrote that the emargination of the anterior pronotal margin is not absent (as Kaszab interpreted) but somewhat smoothed. This emargination looks somewhat smoothed, and it is visible only at a particular inclination of a sample.

We also did not study the holotype of *C. jelineki* deposited in National Museum Prague (Prague, Czech Republic). However, the species is well described and illustrated, and we studied specimens verified by

Figs 1–4. Type specimens of species of *Pachyscelis* Solier, 1836 occurring in Armenia.

1 – *Pimelia musiva*, lectotype (ZIN); 2 – *Brachyscelis gastridula*, lectotype (ZIN); 3 – labels of *Pimelia musiva*; 4 – labels of *Brachyscelis gastridula*.

Рис. 1–4. Типовые экземпляры видов рода *Pachyscelis* Solier, 1836, встречающихся в Армении.

1 – *Pimelia musiva*, лектотип (ZIN); 2 – *Brachyscelis gastridula*, лектотип (ZIN); 3 – этикетки *Pimelia musiva*; 4 – этикетки *Brachyscelis gastridula*.

O. Merkl. We propose the new synonymy *Cyphostethe semenovi* Bogatchev, 1947 = *Cyphostethe jelineki* Merkl, 1991, **syn. n.** given that only one species of *Cyphostethe* Marseul, 1867 occurs in Transcaucasia, and based on the detailed description of *C. semenovi*, determinations and descriptions of Z. Kaszab and O. Merkl.

Distribution. Yerevan and Ararat provinces. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species for Aras valley without clear localities.

Tribe Erodiini Billberg, 1820

Arthrodisia globosus (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Ararat Prov.: 3 ex., Urts Mt. near Armash, 27.04.1933 (Paramonov); 6 ex., Vedi, 10.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); "Goravan Sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1 ex., 30.04.1983, 2 ex., 20.06.1990, 1 ex., 17.06.2013, 8 ex., 13.05.2014 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Ararat and Syunik provinces ([Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011], present data).

Tribe Leptodini Lacordaire, 1859

Leptodes (Mesoleptodes) semenowi Reitter, 1892

Material. Gegharkunik Prov.: 2 ex., Tsapatagh environs (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Shorzha environs, 20.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Martuni, 5.06.1935 (A. Bagdasarian); 1 ex., Zolakar, 7.06.1935 (unknown collector); Sevan town environs, 5.06.1929 (Bochkarev); 2 ex., Sevan town, in houses, 28.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., Babajan, 11.07.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., Yerevan, 15–27.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: Areni environs, "Ptichya" (Areni-1) cave, 39.7314°N / 45.2028°E, 1070 m, 1 ex., 23.05.1987, 8 ex., 15.08–30.10.1987, soil traps (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Shirak (Gyumri) and Vayotsdzor (cave above mentioned) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; it was found also in Gegharkunik Province and Yerevan.

Tribe Pimeliini Latreille, 1802

Pachyscelis musiva (Faldermann in Ménériés, 1832),
sensu lato
(Figs 1–4)

Material. Lori Prov.: 3 ex., Stepanavan, 9.03.1920 (unknown collector). Gegharkunik Prov.: 1 ex., Drakhtik, 10.05.1930 (Kara-Mursa).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Karbi environs, 40.3473°N / 44.3458°E, 1320 m, 18.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., Abovian town, 4–5.07.1904 (E. Koenig); 1 ex., Hadis Mt. near Hatis vill., 1800 m, 1.07.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Abovian town, 20.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 3.08.1928 (M. Makarian); Arzni, 1 ex., 14.04.1927, 1 ex., 1.07.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Geghadir, 1.04.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Gokht, 2.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian); 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 1.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Kaputan, 40.3347°N / 44.6877°E, 1700 m, 30.07.2020 (M. Kalashian);

Armavir Prov.: 4 ex., Parakar, 16–17.04.1925 (M. Rjabov, A. Schelkovnikov); Parakar environs, 1 ex., 28.06.1925, 1 ex., 24.04.1926 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., Metsamor 8.05.1928 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Yervandashat, 3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Bagaran, 30.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Koghbavan, 40.1297°N / 43.7129°E, 1240 m, 6.03.2021 (T. Ghrejyan); 3 ex., Baghranyan environs, 40.1779°N / 43.8389°E, 1070 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan);

Yerevan: 20 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1 ex., 1.03.1909, 1 ex., 14.05.1909, 1 ex., 20.04.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); same locality, 1 ex., 5.06.1933 (Asisian); Yerevan environs, 1 ex., 20.05.1924, 12 ex., 17.04.1927, 1 ex., 30.04.1928, 4 ex., 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 1 ex., 23.04.1924, 1 ex., 25.05.1924, 1 ex., 19.07.1924, 1 ex., 14.04.1926, 1 ex., 11.04.1935 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); Hrazdan River upstream of town, 19.04.1925 (M. Rjabov); 2 ex., Kanaker vill., 17.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Nubarashen, 24.04.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 3.06.1969 (E. Kachvorian); Jrvezh, 1 ex., 11.04.1948, 1 ex., 5.05.1949, 1 ex., 20.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 11.05.1969 (E. Kachvorian).

Ararat Prov.: 2 ex., Vedi environs, 1.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Yeraskh, 5.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 5 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 6–10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); Urts Mt. near Armash, 1 ex., 20.04.1927, 1 ex., 7.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Ararat town, 23.05.1974 (M. Marjanyan).

Syunik Prov.: Meghri, 9.07.1925 (Atajanian); 1 ex., Shvanidzor 38.9902°N / 46.3739°E, 1545 m, 30.04.2021 (G. Karagyan).

Notes. Three subspecies of *Pachyscelis musiva* are listed for Armenia in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020]: *P. m. musiva*, *P. m. gastridula* (Faldermann, 1837) and *P. m. divisa* Reitter, 1893. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded two subspecies for Armenia: *P. m. musiva* and *P. m. gastridula*. This variable species has two terminal morphological characteristics: small elytral primary tubercles not forming clear lines and large elytral tubercles lined up in several longitudinal rows. After examining lectotypes, we interpret the first morphotype as *P. m. musiva* (Figs 1, 3) and the second one as *P. m. gastridula* (Figs 2, 4). The nominotypical subspecies occurs in South Russia (the Pre-Caspian depression), Azerbaijan (except for Nakhichevan), Eastern Georgia and Armenia, and *P. m. gastridula* is widespread in Armenia, Nakhichevan of Azerbaijan, North-Western Iran (Tabriz, Urmia, Sahand Volcano) and Eastern Turkey. However, both extreme forms occur in Armenia, and there are individuals with a full range of transitions between two types of elytral sculpture, even in one population. Therefore, it does not allow us to distinguish these two subspecies clearly. Thus, clarification of the status of subspecies of *P. musiva* is possible only after a detailed study of the male and female genitalia in all populations and with the use of molecular-genetic analysis.

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species from Ararat valley and Syunik (Meghri); new for northern Armenia.

Pimelia (Chaetotoma) cursor Ménériés, 1832

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Aruch (D. Maljushenco).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Abovyan town environs, 26.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 31.05.1934 (G. Ismailov).

Armarir Prov.: 1 ex., steppe near Echmiadzin, 7.04.1935 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); Bagaran, 1 ex., 30.04.1936, 3 ex., 5–6.05.1936 (H. Avetian); Yervandashat, 3 ex., 29.04.1936, 6 ex., 3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Parakar, 11.07.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 17.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., Koghavan, 40.1297°N / 43.7129°E, 1240 m, 6.03.2021 (T. Ghrejjan).

Yerevan: 7 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1 ex., 22.03.1907, 1 ex., 4.05.1909, 1 ex., 18.05.1910, 1 ex., 24.03.1911 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 3 ex., same locality, 13–18.09.1927 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., same locality, 22.08.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., Yerevan environs, 13.07.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); same locality, 1 ex., 17.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 1 ex., 17.06.1928, 1 ex., 21.08.1928 (M. Makarian); 2 ex., Vardavarri Lake environs, 16.05.1924 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Yerevan gardens, 10–11.05.1933 (Asisian); 2 ex., Mushavan, 29.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); Jrvezh, 2 ex., 11.04.1948, 1 ex., 20.06.1948, 1 ex., 17.04.1950, 1 ex., 26.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); Nubarashen, 1 ex., 19.09.1948, 1 ex., 19.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., same locality, 13.04.1969 (E. Kachvorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Avshar, 7.08.1928 (M. Makarian); 1 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 7.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 3.07.1933 (Paramonov); 8 ex., same locality, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan, M. Mazmanyany); 2 ex., Armash environs, 10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., “Khosrov Forest” reserve, Vedi area, 25.06.1964 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., Vedi, 8.04.1979 (R. Ghukasyan); 1 ex., same locality, 20.04.1980 (M. Kalashian); “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 2 ex., 15.06.1979, 1 ex., 17.07.2005 (M. Kalashian); 4 ex., ~5.5 km E Surenavan, 39.8097°N / 44.8354°E, 1245 m, 18–19.07.2014 (M. Kalashian);

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., Selim pass, 2.08.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Areni, 30.07.1978 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species from Armarir Province and Yerevan; found also in Aragatsotn, Kotayk, Ararat and Vayotsdzor provinces.

Pimelia (Chaetotoma) persica Faldermann, 1837

Material. Armavir Prov.: 2 ex., Sardarabad, 3.10.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., same locality, 3.07.1928 (unknown collector); 1 ex., same locality, 2.10.1928 (L. Bekosipov); Parakar, 3 ex., 22.03.1925, 2 ex., 17.04.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 4 ex., same locality, 16.04.1925 (M. Rjabov); Parakar environs, 1 ex., 26.03.1925, 12 ex., 10–11.04.1925, 2 ex., 21–24.09.1925 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); steppe near Echmiadzin, 1 ex., 10.08.1925, 6 ex., 15–20.04.1930, 1 ex., 7.04.1935, 5 ex., 8.08.1935, 3 ex., 18–19.10.1935 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1 ex., Echmiadzin, 19–30.05.1932 (S. Tamamshian); same locality, 2 ex., 2.05.1949, 3 ex., 14.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., Metsamor, 8.05.1928 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., Yervandashat, 27.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 2 ex., Zvartnots vill. environs, Zvartnots monastery ruins, semi-desert, 1.04.1946 (S. Vardanian).

Yerevan: 3 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 4 ex., same locality, 4.08.1904 (E. Koenig); 4 ex., same locality, 1 ex., 1.02.1908, 1 ex., 21.05.1908, 1 ex., 4.03.1909, 1 ex., 16.05.1910, 1 ex., 10.05.1912 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 4 ex., Yerevan environs, 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Yerevan, gardens, 10–11.05.1933 (Asisian).

Ararat Prov.: 3 ex., Yeraskh, 5.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Masis, 31.08.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Ararat town, 14.04.1929 (unknown collector); 4 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 6–7.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Armash, 27.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Artashat, 26.09.1946 (unknown collector); 2 ex., Vedi, 29.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan); 1 ex., same locality, 8.04.1979 (R. Ghukasyan); “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1 ex., 17.06.2013, 10 ex., 13.05.2014 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, same locality, 23.08.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan).

Notes. The species was included to the nominotypical subgenus [Iwan et al., 2020], but in fact, *P. persica* is very similar to *Pimelia capito* Krynicki, 1832 from the subgenus *Chaetotoma* Motschulsky, 1860 and differs only by the structure of meso- and metatarsi [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2021]. Thus, *P. persica* is transferred to the latter subgenus.

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species only from Vedi (Ararat Province); new for Yerevan and Armavir provinces.

Trachyderma (Atrachyderma) setosum
(Faldermann, 1832)

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 2 ex., Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Abovyan, 2.05.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Armarir Prov.: 1 ex., Echmiadzin, 12.07.1906 (A. Kiritshenco); Parakar, 1 ex., 22.03.1925, 5 ex., 17.04–1.05.1925, 1 ex., 10.07.1925, 4 ex., 15–25.09.1925 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., same locality, 1.05.1925 (M. Rjabov); 5 ex., Aratashen, 3.08.1930 (G. Nazarian); 2 ex., same locality, 27.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., steppe near Echmiadzin, 10.03.1935 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 19.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., same locality, 10.10.1978 (R. Ghukasyan).

Yerevan: 27 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., same locality, 4.08.1904 (E. Koenig); 2 ex., same locality, 1–14.05.1907, 1 ex., 21.03.1909, 1 ex., 18.05.1910, 1 ex., 24.05.1912 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1 ex., same locality, 5.06.1933 (Asisian); 6 ex., Vardavarri Lake environs, 16.05.1924 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Yerevan environs, 26.06.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., same locality, 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 5 ex., Mushavan settl., 29.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); Botanical Garden, 8.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 27.04.1996 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., same locality, 4.05.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan).

Ararat Prov.: Vedi environs, 1 ex., 1.06.1926, 3 ex., 20.05.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1 ex., 10.07.2007, 1 ex., 17.06.2013, 1 ex., 13.05.2014 (M. Kalashian); 4 ex., 1♂, same locality, 23.08.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan); 1 ex., ~5.5 km E Surenavan, 39.8097°N / 44.8354°E, 1245 m, 18–19.07.2014 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., Dashtakar, 39.9230°N / 44.7472°E, 965 m, 31.03.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyany); 2 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 39.7960°N, 44.8415°E, 1200 m, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan, M. Mazmanyany).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., 1–2 km E Rind, 17.04.1993 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 2 ex., E Meghri, Artsvakar gorge, 38.05°N / 46.01°E, 650 m, 8.06.2007 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. The species was known from Armavir, Yerevan, Ararat and Syunik provinces [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Kotayk and Vayotsdzor provinces.

Trachyderma christophi christophi (Faust, 1875)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Armavir vill. (D. Maljushenco).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 9.04.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Yerevan environs, 17.06.1924 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 2.06.1973 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Nubarashen, 19.09.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 6.07.1959 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian);

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., Areni environs, "Ptichya" (Areni-1) cave, 39.7314°N / 45.2028°E, 1070 m, soil traps, 15.08–30.10.1987 (M. Kalashian).
Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Meghri, 13.07.1927 (G. Ismailov).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species for Yerevan and Meghri (Syunik Province); new for Armavir, Ararat and Vayotsdzor provinces.

Tribe Stenosini Schaum, 1859

Subtribe Dichillina Reitter, 1916

Aspidocephalus desertus Motschulsky, 1839

Material. Azerbaijan: 1 ex., Nakhichevan, Ordubad, gardens, 20.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. Echmiadzin (ZIN) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]. New for Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic (Azerbaijan).

Dichillus (Dichillocerus) araxidis Reitter, 1889

Material. Yerevan: 1 ex., Nubarashen, 2.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species was known from Armavir (Echmiadzin), Yerevan, Ararat (Vedi) and Syunik (Meghri) provinces [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011].

Dichillus rugatus rugatus Baudi di Selve, 1874

Material. Yerevan: 3 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Jrvezh, 27.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., Nubarashen, 13.06.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 4 ex., N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 27.04.1986 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species from Armavir and Syunik provinces; new for Yerevan.

Oogaster piceus (Ménétriés, 1832)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 5 ex., steppe near Echmiadzin, 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Echmiadzin environs, 24.06.1954 (I. Ioannissian); 1 ex., Karakert environs, 26.07.1996 (K. Aghababian).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Yerevan, 3.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1 ex., Nubarashen, 24.04.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Ararat town environs, formicary of *Cataglyphis setipes* (Forel, 1894), 7.07.1989 (G. Arakelian); 1 ex., "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 29.07.1995 (M. Kalashian); "Khosrov Forest" Reserve, Vedi area, 2 ex., 39.983°N / 44.884°E, 1320 m, 7.07.2000 and 1 ex., 39.9805°N / 44.8792°E, 1310 m, at light, 13–14.07.2003 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species from Syunik Province (Meghri); new for central Armenia.

Subtribe Platamodina Reitter, 1900

Platamodes dentipes dentipes Ménétriés, 1849

Material. Yerevan: 17 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1 ex., 20.03.1907, 2 ex., 03.1909, 1 ex., 20.05.1909, 2 ex., 24.04.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); Nubarashen, 2 ex., 12.05.1948, 3 ex., 24.04.1949, 3 ex., 10.05.1974 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., N of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 27.04.1986 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Jrvezh, 24.05.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 10.05.1974 (M. Marjanyan).
Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Vedi environs, 5.10.1987 (S. Saluk).

Distribution. Yerevan and Echmiadzin (Armavir Province) according to Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011]; new for Ararat Province.

Subtribe Stenosina Schaum, 1859

Stenosis armeniacus (Motschulsky, 1849)

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Ashtarak, 18.06.1980 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Gokht, 2.04.1941 (M. Ter-MinAsian); 1 ex., Abovyan, 2.05.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., W of Geghard monastery, 40.1389°N / 44.8112°E, 1750 m, 23.06.1999 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., E of Hatsavan, 40.1356°N / 44.6732°E, 1520 m, 27.05.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Aravir Prov.: 2 ex., Zvartnots vill., Zvartnots cathedral ruins, soil traps, 10.07.2001 (unknown collector).

Yerevan: 39 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 3 ex., 3.1909, 4 ex., 20–22.03.1910, 2 ex., 14.05.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); Yerevan environs, 1 ex., 10.05.1924, 1 ex., 14.03.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); Nubarashen, 1 ex., 27.04.1948, 1 ex., 24.04.1949, 1 ex., 12.05.1949, 1 ex., 4.04.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); N of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 2 ex., 27.04.1986, 1 ex., 31.03.1988, soil sample (M. Kalashian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Urts Mt. near Armash, 8.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Vedi, 19.06.1982 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., N of Vedi, 39.933°N / 44.717°E, 960 m, 18.06.2002 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., "Khosrov Forest" Reserve, Vedi area, 39.983°N / 44.884°E, 1320 m, 15.10.1991 (M. Kalashian); "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 2 ex., 20.06.1990, 1 ex., 21.05.1996 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded the species from environs of Yerevan and Armavir provinces (Echmiadzin); new for Aragatsotn and Ararat provinces.

Tagenostola pilosa (Motschulsky, 1839)

Distribution. This species is fragmentary distributed in the south of Russia and Transcaucasia [Medvedev, 2008]. On the territory of Armenia it was recorded from Yerevan [Bogatshev, 1938a] and Meghri [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011].

Tribe Tentyriini Eschscholtz, 1831

Calyptopsis caucasica (Kraatz, 1865)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Gyumri (D. Maljushenco).

Tavush Prov.: 1 ex., Koghb, 26.07.1928 (M. Makarian).

Aravir Prov.: Parakar, 4 ex., 4–5.06.1925, 2 ex., 25–28.06.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); steppe near Echmiadzin, 2 ex., 20.04.1930, 9 ex., 10.03.1935, 3 ex., 5.04.1935, 9 ex., 8–14.08.1935, 8 ex., 19.10.1935 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Echmiadzin, 29–30.05.1932 (S. Tamamshian); 2 ex., Yervandashat, 27.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Bagaran, 6.05.1936 (H. Avetian).

Yerevan: 8 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 17.07.1904 (E. Koenig); 1 ex., same locality, 20.03.1909, 1 ex., 14.09.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1 ex., Yerevan environs, 25.01.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 3 ex., Nubarashen, 19.09.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 6 ex., Ararat town, 25.04.1927 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Vedi, 2.05.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Vedi environs, 3.06.1997 (A. Malkhasian); 1 ex., "Goravan Sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 15.07.2013 (M. Kalashian).

Notes. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species for Armavir, Yerevan and Ararat provinces; new for northern Armenia (Shirak and Tavush provinces).

Calyptopsis emarginata Reitter, 1889

Material. Gegharkunik Prov.: 4 ex., Shorzha, 15.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov). Kotayk Prov.: W environs of Geghard monastery, 40.1389°N / 44.8112°E, 1750 m, 1 ex., 20.06.1994, 1 ex., 2.06.2001 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Garni environs, 40.1289°N / 44.6920°E, 1460 m, 19.05.2020 (M. Kalashyan, T. Ghrejjan).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 7.06.1930 (unknown collector); 1 ex., S slope of Odzasar Mt. near Kaghtsrashen, 1.06.1997 (A. Malkhasian); 2 ex., W environs of Paruyr Sevak, 39.7581°N / 44.8934°E, 1120 m, 14.07.1999 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 2 ex., Azatek, 4.06.1972 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., Vernashen environs, 3.06.1979 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 2 ex., S environs of Shvanidzor, abandoned railway station, 27.04.1998 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Shahumyan environs, 39.2140°N / 46.4306°E, 900 m, soil traps, 28.06–01.08.2007 (M. Kalashian).

Notes. Gegharkunik, Yerevan, Ararat and Syunik provinces [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Vayotsdzor Province.

Calyptopsis pulchella pulchella (Faldermarm, 1837)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 5 ex., Yervandashat, 23.04–3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Bagaran, 30.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Hushakert, 28.04.1936 (H. Avetian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., ~6 km ENE Surenavan, 39.8255°N / 44.8383°E, 1480 m, at light, 15.07.2013 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] reported this species for Meghri (Syunik Province); new for Armavir and Ararat provinces.

Dailognatha caraboides (Eschscholtz, 1831)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Ashotsk, 24.08.1937 (G. Avakian); 1 ex., Keti, 17.08.1938 (G. Avakian); 2 ex., Jajur, 25.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 2 ex., Sevan town, 25.08.1926 (Atroschenko); 1 ex., same locality, 15.06.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Drakhtik, 10–12.05.1930 (Kara-Mursa); Sevan Lake, railway station near Sevan Peninsula, 8.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., Sevan Peninsula, 7.04.1971 (A. Karapetian).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 2 ex., Aruch (D. Maljushenco); 3 ex., Byurakan, 7–13.07.1948 (A. Richter); 1 ex., between Antarat and Amberd fortress ruins, 24.09.1978 (R. Ghukasyan); 2 ex., Karbi environs, 40.3421°N / 44.3501°E, 1320 m, 18.10.2020 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., W environs of Agarak, 40.2964°N / 44.2706°E, 1100 m, 26.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 3 ex., Fantan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 13.04.1936 (G. Ismailov); Geghard monastery, 1 ex., 10.08.1926 and 1 ex., 30.05.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 8.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasion); 3 ex., same locality, 2.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 17.05.1971 (A. Karapetian); 2 ex., Arzni, 14.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 2 ex., 8.07.1927, 1 ex., 18.08.1928 (Atroschenko); 3 ex., Kotayk vill., 3.08.1928 (M. Makarian); 3 ex., Garni, 1.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 2 ex., Garni, 3.05.1979 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Garni environs, 40.1289°N / 44.6912°E, 1460 m, 25.04.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejjan); 2 ex., NE environs of Geghadir, 1–8.08.1997 (A. Malkhasyan); 1 ex., Kaputan, 40.3347°N / 44.6877°E, 1700 m, 30.07.2020 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: Parakar, 3 ex., 2–16.06.1925, 2 ex., 27.07.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., steppe near Echmiadzin, 13.08.1935 (A. Schelkovnikov); 5 ex., Yervandashat, 26.04.1936 (Shcherbakova); 1 ex., Echmiadzin, 2.04.1938 (Aloian); 3 ex., Baghramyran environs, 40.1779°N / 43.8389°E, 1070 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyany).

Yerevan: 17 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 19.04.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskiy); 1 ex., same locality, 13.11.1939 (A. Richter); 1 ex., same locality, 9.08.1980 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., hills up to Hrazdan River, 2.04.1922 (unknown collector); Yerevan environs, 1 ex., 21.06.1924, 2 ex., 13.07.1924, 1 ex., 30.04.1928, 1 ex., 8.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); Jrvezh, 1 ex., 16.05.1948, 1 ex., 16.04.1950, 1 ex., 7.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); Nubarashen, 1 ex., 27.06.1948, 1 ex., 12.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 4.05.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Urts Mt. near Armash, 8.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Vedi, 25.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan); 1 ex., ~3 km NE Tigranashen, 39.8061°N / 44.9715°E, 1680 m, 29.06.2001 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, Azat water body, 40.0816°N / 44.6287°E, 1060 m, 24.04.2021 (M. Kalashian); 4 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejjan, M. Mazmanyany).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., Rind, 1.07.1979 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., NE environs of Vayk, between 39.6890°N / 45.4941°E, 1320 m, and 39.6946°N / 45.4974°E, 1505 m, 10.10.2014 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Meghri, 30.06.1925 (Atajanian); 2 ex., NW environs of Vardanidzor, abandoned vill. Lichkvaz, 20–28.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Karchevan, 12.09.1936 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1 ex., N environs of Shvanidzor, Gyumarants site, 38.9901°N / 46.3739°E, 1560 m, 3.05.2021 (G. Karagyan).

Distribution. All territory of Armenia.

Dailognatha pumila (Baudi di Selve, 1874)

Material. Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., ~6 km ENE Surenavan, 39.8255°N / 44.8383°E, 1480 m, at light, 15.07.2013 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 2 ex., Gnishik, 2100 m, 27.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Martiros, 2400 m, 18.05.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. Aragatsotn (Arailer Mt.) and Vayotsdzor (Martiros) provinces according to Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011]; new for Ararat Province.

Gnathosia modesta (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Syunik Prov.: Meghri, 2 ex., 30.04.1938 and 1 ex., 23.07.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian); between Meghri and Karchevan, 3.06.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., W environs of Meghri, 3.06.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., NNE environs of Meghri, Kaladash Mt., 16.05.1972 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., Meghri environs, 6.06.1993 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Alvank environs, 19.07.1997 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Yerevan, Armavir, Ararat and Syunik provinces [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011].

Microdera sp.

Note. The taxon listed as *M. ocularis* Reitter, 1915 from Armenia (Echmiadzin) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011] is a new species, which will be described in a separate taxonomic revision.

Tentyria striatopunctata Ménétrière, 1832

Material. Shirak Prov.: 2 ex., Gyumri (D. Maljushenco); 3 ex., W environs of Marmashen, 9.05.1990 (M. Kalashian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1 ex., Karchaghbyur environs, 16.08.1978 (M. Kalashian).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Talin (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., Ushi environs, 8.04.1979 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Hrazdan town (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Arzni, 14.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Kotayk vill., 3.08.1928 (M. Makarian); 2 ex., Abovyan town, 2.05.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., 2–4 km S Hatsavan, 12.07.2006 (K. Yeranyan);

Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Metsamor, 25.05.1928 (unknown collector); 3 ex., Aratashen, 3.08.1930 (G. Nazarian); 1 ex., same locality, 27.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 4 ex., Yervandashat 3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 5 ex., Bagaran, 5.05.1936 (H. Avetian);

Yerevan: 7 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); Yerevan environs, 1 ex., 23.06.1924, 1 ex., 5.03.1926 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., Nubarashen, 19.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Zoo, 27.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 3 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., Armash environs, 10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Urts Mt. near Armash, 27.06.1933 (Paramonov); 1 ex., "Goravan Sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 17.06.2013 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., NE environs of Masis, 40.0729°N / 44.4545°E, 840 m, 5.06.2014 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Armash fishery ponds, 39.7611°N / 44.7522°E, 810 m, 11.07.2020 (T. Ghrejjan); 2 ex., Surenavan environs, 39.7967°N / 44.8022°E, 980 m, 11.07.2020 (T. Ghrejjan).

Distribution. Widely distributed in Armenia. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species for Armenia without localities.

Tentyria tessulata tessulata Tauscher, 1812

Material. Shirak Prov.: 9 ex., Gyumri environs, 18.04.1919 (unknown collector); 2 ex., same locality, 30.05.1930 (H. Wasakian); 1 ex., Jajur, 29.07.1937 (unknown collector); 1 ex., same locality, 25.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 2 ex., Gilli Lake, 9.07.1921 (A. Schelkovnikov); 6 ex., Areguni environs, 17.07.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); Drakhtik environs, 18 ex., 16.07.1927, 22 ex., 10.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 3 ex., same locality, 18.04.1930 (Kara-Mursa); 1 ex., same locality, 40.5542°N / 45.2222°E, 1950 m, 8.05.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian); 20 ex., S slope near Drakhtik, 2900 m, 18.04.1930 (unknown collector); Shorza environs, 9 ex., 20.06.1928, 24 ex., 15.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 5 ex., Tsapatagh environs, 15.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 5 ex., same locality, 12.04.1930 (Kara-Mursa); 1 ex., same locality, 40.3968°N / 45.4946°E, 2010 m, 7.07.2020 (M. Mazmanyan); 1 ex., Ayrk, 20.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Noratus, 13.09.1952 (G. Avakian); 2 ex., Karchaghbyur environs, 16.08.1978 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., Lake Sevan, Artanish peninsula, 13.06.1982 (M. Kalashian).

Aragsotsn Prov.: 4 ex., Talin (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Ushi environs, 8.04.1979 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 6 ex., Hrazdan town (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Garni River near Geghard monastery, 30.05.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 15.08.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., Garni, 20.04.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Garni, 1.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Garni environs, 40.1289°N / 44.6912°E, 1460 m, 25.04.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian); 3 ex., Geghadir, 1.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 2 ex., Bjni environs, 26.04.2006 (G. Karagyan);

Armavir Prov.: 3 ex., Parakar, 16.04.1925 (M. Rjabov); same locality, 2 ex., 11.03.1925, 2 ex., 30.03.1925, 3 ex., 9.04.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); steppe near Echmiadzin, 1 ex., 19.10.1925, 1 ex., 15.04.1930, 5 ex., 20.04.1930, 3 ex., 20.10.1935, 5 ex., 7.12.1935 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Echmiadzin, 29–30.05.1932 (S. Tamamshian); 3 ex., Metsamor, 8.05.1928 (unknown collector); 1 ex., steppe near Lucashin, 16.05.1928 (M. Makarian); 1 ex., Sardarapat, 7.10.1928 (L. Bekosipov); Yervandashat, 7 ex., 27–29.04.1936, 2 ex., 3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); Bagaran, 3 ex., 5–6.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Armavir town, 7.06.1951 (G. Avakian); 3 ex., Baghranyan environs, 40.1779°N / 43.8389°E, 1070 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan).

Yerevan: 27 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); Yerevan environs, 1 ex., 18.03.1926, 4 ex., 14.05.1926 (unknown collector); same locality, 5 ex., 30.04.1927, 1 ex., 30.04.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Hrazdan river upstream of town, 19.04.1925 (M. Rjabov); 4 ex., Kanaker (now ruins), 19.04.1926 (unknown collector); 2 ex., Kanaker-Zeytun County, 14.11.1947 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 5 ex., Mushavan settlement, 29.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); 6 ex., Jrvezh, 2.06.1936 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., same locality, 22.08.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 7 ex., same locality, 25.04.1971 (A. Karapetyan); Nubarashen, 1 ex., 19.09.1948, 1 ex., 24.04.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 13.04.1969 (E. Kachvorian); same locality, 4 ex., 7.03.1971 (A. Karapetyan).

Ararat Prov.: 5 ex., Marmarashen, 23.03.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Ararat town environs, 25.04.1927 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Armash environs, 10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 10 ex., Urts Mt. near Armash, 8.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Yeraskh, 8.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., "Goravan Sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1 ex., 29.04.1991 and 6 ex., 13.05.2014 (M. Kalashian); 3 ex., same locality, 31.03.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan); 2 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, near Azat water body, 40.0862°N / 44.6251°E, 1080 m, 19.05.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian);

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., Geger, 23.05.1908 (D. Maljushenco); 3 ex., Saravan, 24.07.1927 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Rind environs, 1.06.1979 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Meghri, 10.05.1938 (M. Ter-Grigorian); same locality, 1 ex., 20.05.1938, 3 ex., 6–10.06.1938 (Marutyan); 1 ex., Lichk, 13.06.1965 (G. Avakian); 1 ex., Shvanidzor, 38.9902°N / 46.3739°E, 1545 m, 30.04.2021 (G. Karagyan).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species for Aras valley and environs of Sevan Lake without localities; actually occurs in all provinces of Armenia excluding Lori and Tavush.

Tribe Zophosini Solier, 1834

Zophosis (Oculosis) punctata punctata Brullé, 1832

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 2 ex., Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., Abovyan town, 4.07.1904 (E. Koenig); 1 ex., Abovyan town environs, 25.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 15.08.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., SW environs of Gokht, Havuts Tar Monastery ruins, 9.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 40.1223°N / 44.7680°E, 1560 m, 15.04.1979 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., 4 km S Hatsavan, 40.0952°N / 44.6342°E, 1150 m, 23.06.2004 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., E environs of Geghadir, 40.1516°N / 44.6698°E, 1720 m, 23.04.2016 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Garni environs, 40.1289°N / 44.6912°E, 1460 m, 25.04.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian).

Armavir Prov.: 7 ex., Yervandashat, 26.04–3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Hushakert, 28.04.1936 (H. Avetian); Bagaran, 1 ex., 30.04.1936, 1 ex., 5.05.1936 (H. Avetian).

Yerevan: 3 ex., Jrvezh, 2.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); same locality, 1 ex., 6.06.1948, 1 ex., 17.07.1949, 1 ex., 14.07.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 25.04.1971 (A. Karapetian); Nubarashen, 1 ex., 24.04.1949, 1 ex., 19.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species for Armavir, Kotayk and Ararat provinces; new for Yerevan.

Zophosis (Septentriophosis) rugosa Faldermann, 1837

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Garni, 1.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 15.05.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Armavir Prov.: 3 ex., Aratashen, 11.09.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); Parakar, 1 ex., 28.03.1925, 2 ex., 7.04.1925, 2 ex., 9.04.1925, 2 ex., 30.03.1925, 1 ex., 4.06.1925, 1 ex., 16.07.1925, 5 ex., 24.04.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); steppe near Echmiadzin, 3 ex., 5.07.1925, 4 ex., 20.04.1930, 2 ex., 7.04.1935, 5 ex., 10.08.1935, 3 ex., 19.10.1935 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1 ex., Echmiadzin, 29–30.05.1930 (S. Tamamshian); 7 ex., Metsamor, 8.05.1928 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 3 ex., Lukashin environs, 16.05.1928 (M. Makarian); 2 ex., Sardarapat, 7.10.1928 (L. Bekosipov); 1 ex., Yervandashat, 27.04.1936 (Shcherbak); 1 ex., Hushakert, 28.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 2 ex., Bagaran, 30.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Shahumyan, 14.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., Armavir, 13.08.1950 (G. Avakian); 5 ex., same locality, 13.05.1969 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1 ex., Zvartnots vill. environs, Zvartnots Cathedral ruins, 1.06.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 5 ex., Baghranyan environs, 40.1779°N / 43.8389°E, 1070 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan).

Yerevan: 129 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 17.07.1904 (E. Koenig); same locality, 1 ex., 24.09.1909, 1 ex., 25.09.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); Yerevan environs, 3 ex., 14.05.1926, 1 ex., 30.04.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., hills up to Hrazdan River, 2.04.1922 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Yerevan, gardens, 10–11.05.1933 (Asisian); Nubarashen, 2 ex., 27.06.1948, 1 ex., 24.04.1949, 1 ex., 19.09.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 4.05.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian); Jrvezh, 2 ex., 20.06.1948 and 1 ex., 4.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: Armash environs, Asni ruins, 7.06.1908 (D. Maljushenco); 4 ex., same locality, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, M. Mazmanyan); 2 ex., Vedi, 4.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 29.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan); Urts Mt. near Armash, 3 ex., 28.05.1927, 1 ex., 8.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 27.06.1933 (Paramonov); Yeraskh, 1 ex., 5.06.1928, 4 ex., 9.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Ararat town, 23.05.1974 (M. Marjanyan); "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1 ex., 15.04.1979, 2 ex., 21.04.1988, 1 ex., 17.06.2008 (M. Kalashian); 3 ex., same locality, 31.03.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan); 2 ex., Dashtakar, 39.9230°N / 44.7472°E, 965 m, 31.03.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan).

Distribution. Ararat and Armavir provinces (Vedi, Oktemberyan) according to Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011]; additionally recorded from Yerevan and Kotayk Province.

Subfamily Lagriinae Latreille, 1825

Tribe Belopini Reitter, 1917

Centorus filiformis Motschulsky, 1872

Material. Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 8.06.1925 (unknown collector); 4 ex., same locality, 6.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-

Khznorian); 1 ex., Taronik, 8.06.1925; 4 ex., Jrarat, "Vordan karmir" Sanctuary, 40.0762°N / 44.2405°E, 840 m, 18.03.1988 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 1 ex., Nubarashen, 17.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1.08.1988 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Tsav, light trap, 19.06.1970 (S. Pustovarov).

Distribution. South-western Armenia, halophytic habitats.

Centorus trogospita Motschulsky, 1872

Material. Armavir Prov.: 5 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 21.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: 1 ex., Yerevan, 24.05.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1 ex., Tsitsernakaber park, 7.08.1980 (M. Kalashian).

Ararat Prov.: 4 ex., Ararat town environs, salt marshes, 7.04.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. South-western Armenia, halophytic habitats.

Tribe Cossyphini Latreille, 1802

Cossyphus tauricus Fischer von Waldheim, 1832

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 2 ex., Karbi environs, 40.3473°N / 44.3458°E, 1320 m, 18.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 6 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., same locality, 10.05.1922 (F. Dobzhansky); 3 ex., Jrvezh, 2.04.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., Nubarashen, 10.05.1974 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0972°N / 44.5482°E, 1140 m, 13.03.2016 (M. Kalashian); 6 ex., E border of Yerevan, near Jrashen settlement, 13.05.1988 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Yerevan and Armavir Province (Echmiadzin) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Aragatsotn Province.

Tribe Laenini Seidlitz, 1895

Laena ferruginea Küster, 1846

Type material. 1♂, holotype of *Laena constricta* Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1957 with the Cyrillic label: "Ереван, Араздаян, АССР, 15.05.54" (Yerevan, Arazdayan [= Yeraskh], Armenian SSR, 15.05.19[54] [leg. S. Iablokoff-Khznorian]) and with additional labels: "typus" (Iablokoff-Khznorian' hand), "*Laena constricta* Khnz." (Iablokoff-Khznorian' hand) and "Holotypus, *Laena constricta* Khznorian, 1957, M. Kalashian det., 2021" (printed on red paper).

Material. Yerevan: Yerevan, 1 ex., 03.1909, 2 ex., 1.06.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1 ex., between Yerevan and Nubarashen, 25.03.1948 (A. Richter, M. Ter-Minasian); Jrvezh, 1 ex., 11.04.1947, 2 ex., 11.04.1948, 2 ex., 11.04.1952, 1 ex., 9.05.1952, 1 ex., 25.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 5.04.1971 (A. Karapetyan); Nubarashen, 6 ex., 4.04.1952, 1 ex., 2.05.1960 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); N environs of Nubarashen, 2 ex., 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 21.04.1993, and 2 ex., 40.0972°N / 44.5482°E, 1140 m, 13.03.2016 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., "Erebuni" Reserve, 40.1435°N / 44.6207°E, 1420 m, 13.03.2016 (M. Kalashian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, 40.0990°N / 44.6334°E, 1–2.05.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Notes. The species is included into the Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia (as *L. constricta* Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1957) [Kalashyan, 2010b].

The species *L. constricta* was recently synonymized with *L. ferruginea* Küster, 1846 by Schawaller [2020]. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko interpreted (under question) *L. constricta* as a junior synonym of *L. baudii* Weise, 1878 (described from Georgia: Azureti and Likhi Range). Here we leave Schawaller's taxonomic interpretation until the examination of the type material.

Distribution. Western and southern Armenia [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011; Schawaller, 2020].

Laena lederi Weise, 1878

Type material. 1 ex., holotype of *L. bogatshevi* Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1984 with the Cyrillic label: "Алаверди, Шамлуг, АССР, 3.6.49" (Alaverdi, Shamlug, Armenian SSR, 3.06.19[49] [leg. S. Iablokoff-Khznorian]) and with additional labels: "typus" (Iablokoff-Khznorian' hand), "*Laena bogatshevi* Khnz." (bottom label, Iablokoff-Khznorian's hand) and "Holotypus, *Laena bogatshevi* Khznorian, 1984, M. Kalashian det., 2021" (printed on red paper).

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Ashotsk, 6.07.1992 (M. Kalashian).

Note. See information on the synonymy omitted in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020] in Table 1.

Distribution. The species is known only from forests of the northern part of Armenia.

Laena wanensis Schuster, 1940

Material. Syunik Prov.: 2 ex., Shrunukh, 14.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 4 ex., Chakaten, 24.06.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Shikahogh State Reserve, Mtnadzor area, 23.07.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 7 ex., Shishkert, 10.05.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Shahumyan environs, 39.2227°N / 46.4291°E, 945 m, soil traps, 7.06–18.07.2014 (G. Karagyan).

Note. Iablokoff-Khznorian [1957] interpreted this species as *Laena piligera* Weise, 1878, which was described from "Kaukasus". Schawaller [2020] interpreted this species from Armenia and Turkey as *L. wanensis*. Here we leave Schawaller's taxonomic interpretation until the examination of the type material.

Tribe Lagriini Latreille, 1825

Lagria hirta (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1♀, Jajur environs, 4.08.2020 (M. Arakelyan).

Lori Prov.: 2♂, 2♀, Stepanavan, 14.07.1920 (unknown collector); 1♀, Stepanavan environs, Medvezh'ya Mt., 31.07.1920 (unknown collector); 1♂, 1♀, Akhtala environs, 25.08.1925 (unknown collector); 2♂, 1♀, Shamlugh, 15.08.1932 (A. Schelkovnikov, Kara-Mursa); 2♀, road from Shamlugh to Akhtala, 17.08.1932 (Kara-Mursa); 1♂, Marts, 19.07.1937 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1♂, 3♀, Pambak, 6–9.07.1980 (N. Manukyan); 1♂, 2♀, Gyulagarak environs, 9.07.2020 (M. Arakelyan).

Tavush Prov.: 1♀, Dilijan, 9.07.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 5♂, 1♀, same locality, 11–25.07.2026 (G. Izmailov); same locality, 14–15.07.1928 (Makarjan); 2♀, same locality, 19.08.1928 (O. Botarskaia); 1♂, 1♀, Yenokavan, 20.07.1978 (M. Kalashian); N environs of Tegut vill., Haghartsin monastery, 40.8043°N / 44.8895°E, 1550 m, 2.07.2005 (M. Kalashian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 4♂, Tsovaguyugh environs, 12.07.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 1♀, Drakhtik environs, 16.07.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Sevan city, Botanical Garden, 25.07.1963 (G. Harutyunian); 1♀, Kalavan, 40.6504°N / 45.1111°E, 1580 m, 19.07.2020 (T. Ghrejan).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♀, Kuchak, 26.07.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1♂, 1♀, same locality, 19.07.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Kotayk Prov.: 5♂, 5♀, Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljuchenco); 1♂, Hankavan, 3.08.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1♀, Sevaberd environs, Yelija fields, 24.07.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Abovyan town environs, 10.08.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Arzakan environs, Aghveran recreation area, 22.07.1976 (A. Karapetian).

Armavir Prov.: 1♀, Parakar, 17.07.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 1♀, Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 6.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian). Yerevan: Zoo, 1♂, 2.07.1957, 1♂, 1♀, 13.09.1957 (S. Vardikian).

Syunik Prov.: 1♂, Goris, 1.08.1926 (G. Izmailov); 1♀, same locality, 15.06.1941 (H. Avetian); 2♀, same locality, 30.05.1965 (G. Harutyunian); 1♂, Karchevan, 12.09.1936 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1♂, 1♀, Tsav, 29.07.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, E environs of Goris, 39.5199°N / 46.3559°E, 1620 m, 21.08.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan).

Distribution. All territory of Armenia.

Subfamily Blaptinae Leach, 1815

Tribe Blaptini Leach, 1815

Blaps araxicola Seidlitz, 1893

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 1♂, Geghard monastery, 15.08.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: 1♂, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco).

Ararat Prov.: Vedi, 1 ♂, 7.05.1959, 3♂, 1♀, 12.09.1974, 1♂, 4♀, 28.04.1975 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 4♂, 5♀, same locality, 29.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan); 1♂, 3♀, "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, borrows of *Meriones* sp., 12–14.11.1958 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 5♂, Urtsadzor, 20.09.1974 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. I. Chigray and Nabozhenko [2016] listed this species only from Vedi environs (Goravan sands, Ararat Province); new for Yerevan and Kotayk Province.

Blaps kovali Abdurakhmanov et Nabozhenko, 2011

See type material in Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011].

Material. Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♂, 1♀, Areni environs, "Ptichya" (Areni-1) cave, 39.7314°N / 45.2028°E, 1070 m, 30.10.1987 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. The species is known only from the type locality [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011].

Blaps lethifera pterotapha Fischer von Waldheim
in Ménétrié, 1832

Material. Shirak Prov.: 3♂, Panik (D. Maljushenco); 6♂, 3♀, Gyumri, 9–10.1921 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 2♂, 2♀, Gyumri environs, 25–30.05.1930 (H. Nasanian); 1♀, Ketik, 17.08.1938 (G. Avakian); 1♀, Artik, 26.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Lori Prov.: Stepanavan, 1♂, 2♀, 14.05.1920, 1♂, 3♀, 10–14.07.1920, 1♂, 21.05.1922 (unknown collector); 2♂, 2♀, Ardvi, 29.06–12.07.1922 (unknown collector); 3♂, 2♀, same locality, 3–8.08.1937 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1♂, 2♀, Vanadzor, 1♂, 19.10.1949 and 1♂, 2♀, 17.12.1949 (L. Tovmasian).

Tavush Prov.: 1♂, Idjevan, 21.06.1934 (Vartanian); 1♂, N environs of Teghut, 3 km S Haghartsin monastery, 25.07.2005 (M. Kalashian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1♂, Sevan town (D. Maljushenco); 1♀, same locality, 7.08.1925 (M. Ryabov); 1♀, Gavar, 31.07.1925 (G. Ismailov); 2♂, 2♀, Sevan town environs, 10–12.07.1926 (Atroschenko); same locality, 3♂, 2♀, 14.06.1927, 2♂, 10.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, same locality, 5.06.1929 (Bockarev); Drakhtik, 7♂, 7♀, 16.07.1927, 1♂, 1♀, 10.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Ayrk, 20.08.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); Shorzha environs, 3♂, 11♀, 20.06.1928, 2♂, 2♀, 11–15.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, N environs of Shorzha, 40.5113°N / 45.2682°E, 2000 m, 5.06.2020 (T. Ghredjian); Tsapatagh, 2♂, 7–15.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, same locality, 12.04.1930 (Kara-Mursa); 1♂, 1♀, Gilli (former lake, now fields), 9–11.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Nshkhark, 1.07.1939 (G. Avakian); 1♂, Lchashen, 2.07.1980 (N. Khazhakyan); 1♂, Aghberk, 40.5148°N / 45.2684°E, 2010 m, 5.08.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian).

Araratsov Prov.: 1♂, Ashtarak, 17.06.1928 (unknown collector); 1♂, Karmrashen, 30.05.1969 (E. Kachvorian); 1 ex., Kosh environs, 24.05.1996 (A. Malkhasyan).

Kotayk Prov.: 1♀, Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 1♂, 3♀, Abovyan town environs, 26–30.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♀, Getamej, 15–20.07.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 4♀, Arzni, 14.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 3♂, 3♀, Garni, 30.05–1.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1♂, Garni environs, 40.1289°N / 44.6912°E, 1460 m, 25.04.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian); 2♂, Geghard monastery, 31.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1♂, same locality, 11.05.1939 (M. Aloian); 1♂, 1♀, N environs of Geghadir, 10.07.1996 (A. Malkhasyan); 1♀, Sevaberd, 11.07.2002 (Expedition of Antiplague Center).

Armavir Prov.: Parakar, 1♂, 4♀, 24–30.03.1925, 2♀, 7–9.04.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♂, 2♀, Aratashen, 1.06.1925 (unknown collector); 1♀, steppe near Ecmiadzin, 10.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Ecmiadzin, 12.06.1975 (M. Kalashian); 2♀, Yervandashat, 26.04.1936 (Shcherbakova); 2♂, same locality, 3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1♂, Baghranyan environs, 40.1779°N / 43.8389°E, 1070 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan).

Yerevan: Yerevan, 1♂, 19.05.1910, 1♀, 20.06.1910, 1♀, 20.05.1911, 1♂, 18.06.1911 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1♂, same locality, 13.03.1979 (M. Kalashian); Yerevan environs, 1♂, 2♀, 23.04.1924, 1♂, 10.07.1924, 1♂, 1♀, 10.07.1925, 1♀, 30.04.1928, 1♂, 15.04.1930, 1♂, 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 3♀, Kanaker vill., 15.04.1908 (D. Maljushenco); 2♂, same locality, 17.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Mushavan settl., 29.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); Nubarashen, 1♀, 13.04.1969, 1♂, 3.06.1969 (E. Kachvorian); 1♀, same locality, 7.03.1971 (A. Karapetian); 1♂, same locality, 24.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan); 1♂, N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 31.03.1988 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, 1♀, Jrvezh, 25.04.1971 (A. Karapetian).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, Artashat, 7.04.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♂, 1♀, same locality, 26.04.1949 (A. Harutyunian); 1♂, 1♀, Vedi, 1.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 3♀, same locality, 21.05.1975 (M. Marjanyan); 1♂, same locality, 18.04.1995 (A. Malkhasyan); 1♀, Ararat town environs, 25.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 1♀, Armash, 10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, "Khosrov Forest" Reserve, Vedi area, 1.06.1972 (A. Karapetian); 1♀, Surenavan environs, 39.8169°N / 44.7424°E, 810 m, 27.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♂, Vernasen, 29.04.1978 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, Rind, 4.11.1979 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1♂, NW environs of Vardanidzor, abandoned Lichkvaz vill., 3.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Kapan environs, 7.08.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Vardanidzor, 17.04.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, NNE environs of Meghri, Kaladash Mt., 18.04.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); Meghri, 1♀, 26.04.1954, 1♂, 3.05.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. Everywhere in Armenia.

Blaps mortisaga (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material. Lori Prov.: 1♂, Spitak (D. Maljushenco); Stepanavan, 2♀, 10.07.1920, 1♂, 9.08.1920 (unknown collector); 1♀, Vanadzor, 7.09.1936 (G. Avakian).

Tavush Prov.: 1♀, Achajur environs, 28.08.1978 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, Yenokavan environs, Lastiver Campground, 40.9032°N / 45.0610°E, 1130 m, 26.06.1980 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, N environs of Teghut village, Haghartsin monastery, 40.8043°N / 44.8895°E, 1550 m, soil traps, 1–27.07.2005 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Ditavan, 40.9745°N / 45.2129°E, 752 m, 23.08.2015 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghredjian, G. Karagyan).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1♂, 1♀, Drakhtik, 16.07.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); Tsapatagh, 1♂, 29.07.1927, 1♂, 2♀, 5.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 1♂, 1♀, 18.04.1930 (Kara-Mursa).

Araratsov Prov.: 5♂, 2♀, Kuchak (D. Maljushenco); 1♂, same locality, 9.08.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Kotayk Prov.: 1♂, S environs of Garni, abandoned Alakre vill., 11.06.1997 (A. Malkhasyan); 1♀, W environs of Geghard monastery, 40.1404°N / 44.8193°E, 1760 m, 16.07.2014 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: 1♂, Taronik, 14.09.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 2♂, steppe near Ecmiadzin, 15–20.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 9.10.1978 (R. Ghukasyan).

Yerevan: 1♂, Yerevan, 20.05.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); Yerevan environs, 2♂, 23.04.1924, 1♀, 2.05.1924, 1♀, 11.07.1925, 1♀, 15.02.1926, 1♂, 1♀, 20.09.1926, 1♀, 4.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Kanaker-Zeytun County, 6.04.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Botanical Garden, 20.10.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, Vedi, 1.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♀, Areni environs, "Ptichya" (Areni-1) cave, 39.7314°N / 45.2028°E, 1070 m, soil traps, 15.08–30.10.1987 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1♂, NW environs of Vardanidzor, abandoned Lichkvaz vill., 10.07.1925 (Atajanian); Kajaran, 1♂, 1860 m, 20.07.1929, 1♂, 1♀, 1950 m, 30.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Meghri, 12.05.1938 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1♂, N Karmrakar, 39.3279°N / 46.4721°E, 1390 m, soil traps, 15.06–20.07.2004 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, S environs of Khndzoresk (old village), 1500–1800 m, 12.08.2007 (M. Kalashian).

Notes. *Blaps puella* Allard, 1881 was described from "Kurdistan", but the country is unknown. This species was recorded for Armenia [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]. The study of a large material from Armenia and Turkey showed that this species is probably conspecific to *B. mortisaga* and has not differences from the latter in the structure of male genitalia, female genital tubes and ovipositor. Specimens determined as *B. puella* in collections of ZIN and HNHM have shorter mucron and narrower pronotum. However, specimens with transitional characters do not allow us to interpret *B. puella* as a separate species. The apparent hiatus between *B. puella* and *B. mortisaga* is not expressed when studying large series of beetles with an entire variability. Thus, we preliminary interpret *B. mortisaga* and *B. puella* as one species. A separate taxonomic revision will present complete argumentation with illustrations and information on type specimens.

Distribution. Everywhere in Armenia.

Blaps ominosa Ménériés, 1832

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♂, Talin environs, 10.07.1928 (O. Amirdjanian).

Armavir Prov.: 1♂, Parakar, 16.04.1925 (M. Ryabov); same locality, 7♂, 2♀, 17–18.04.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 2♂, 23–24.09.1925, 4♂, 2♀, 22–24.04.1926 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1♂, 1♀, Zvartnots vill. environs, semidesert, 1.06.1946 (S. Vardikian); 1♀, Echmiadzin, 2.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: 13♂, 12♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♂, 20.06.1908, 1♀, 21.04.1909, 1♂, 22.05.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); Yerevan environs, 1♂, 10.05.1924, 4♂, 5♀, 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♂, Vardavarri Lake environs, 16.05.1924 (G. Ismailov); Jrvezh, 1♂, 31.05.1948, 1♀, 30.09.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, Ararat town, 25.04.1927 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1♂, Urts Mt. near Armash, 30.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 3♂, 2♀, Armash environs, Asni ruins, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, at light, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan, M. Mazmanyany); Vedi, 4♂, 4♀, 1.06.1926, 2♂, 20.05.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, same locality, hammada, 12.09.1974 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, 2♀, Vedi environs, 24.05.1995 (K. Agababyan); 1♂, Ararat railway station, 8.09.1965 (M. Vinogradov, G. Avetisian); “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1♂, 1♀, 22.10.1986, 2♂, 29.04.1999, 2♂, 10–11.07.2007 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, same locality, 23.08.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan); 1♀, W environs of Dashtakar, 39.9234°N / 44.7470°E, 960 m, 18.08.2015 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghredjyan, G. Karagyan).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♂, Rind, 3.11.1979 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1♂, E environs of Shvanidzor, 38.9333°N / 46.3833°E, 720 m, 17.08.2003 (K. Yeranyan).

Distribution. The species was reported from Yerevan, Armavir and Ararat provinces [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Aragatsotn and Syunik provinces.

Blaps pudica Ballion, 1888

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Ashotsk (D. Maljushenco).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 34 ex., Sevan town (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 25.08.1924 (Atroschenko); Sevan town environs, 2 ex., 14.06.1927, 3 ex., 10.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, same locality, 3.06.1988 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Tsapatagh, 15.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 12.04.1930 (Kara-Mursa); 1♀, Tsovaguyugh, 20.08.2002 (Expedition of Antiplague Center); 1 ex., Gegharkunik vill., 40.2489°N / 45.1543°E, 2180 m, 16.05.2021 (T. Ghrejan, M. Mazmanyany, G. Karagyan).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Kuchak, 25.07.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Tsaghakdzor (D. Maljushenco); 1♂, N environs of Geghadir, 10.07.1996 (A. Malhasian); 1♂, 1♀, Sevaber, 11.07.2002 (Expedition of Antiplague Center).

Yerevan: Yerevan, 1 ex., 14.05.1908, 3 ex., 14–27.04.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., Selim Pass, 11.08.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Yeghgnadzor, 21.07.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Syunik Prov.: 2 ex., Kajaran, 1950m, 30.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 1♀, Vorotan Pass, 23.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Srashen, 23.04.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Noravan environs, 39.5454°N / 46.0937°E, 1865 m, 22.08.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan); 1 ex., Tsg huk environs, 39.6731°N / 45.8770°E, 2250 m, 22.08.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan).

Distribution. I. Chigray and Nabozhenko [2016] listed this species for Shirak, Kotayk and Syunik provinces of Armenia; actually, it was found also in Gegharkunik, Aragatsotn, Yerevan and Vayotsdzor provinces.

Blaps taeniolata Ménériés, 1832

Material. Ararat Prov.: 2♂, E environs of Bardzrashen, Azat water body, 40.066°N / 44.617°E, 1070 m, 3.05.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Yerevan [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Ararat Province. The species has a tendency to synanthropic lifestyle and can be found in any regions of Armenia.

Tribe Dendarini Mulsant et Rey, 1854

Dendarus (Pandarinus) crenulatus (Ménériés, 1832)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1♂, W environs of Marmashen, 24.05.1992 (M. Kalashian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: Sevan Lake, Sevan Peninsula (former island, now peninsula), 1♂, 4.07.1923, 1♂, 30.07.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1♂, Areguni, 17.07.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1♂, Vardenis, 31.07.1925 (G. Ismailov); 2♂, Tsapatagh, 12.04.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); Drakhtik, 26.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, same locality, 18.04.1930 (Kara-Mursa); 1♂, same locality, 40.5542°N / 45.2222°E, 1950 m, 8.05.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejan); 1♂, Tsovaguyugh, 29.08.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Tsovaguyugh environs, 40.6405°N / 44.9628°E, 2130 m, 15.05.2021 (T. Ghrejan, M. Mazmanyany, G. Karagyan).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♀, Aruch (D. Maljushenco); 1♀, between Antarut and Amberd fortress ruins, 24.09.1978 (R. Ghukasyan); NW environs of Yegvard, SE slope of Arailer Mt., between 40.3681°N / 44.4687°E, 1680 m and 40.3893°N / 44.4678°E, 2200 m, 2♂, 1♀, 21.05.1991, 3♂, 3♀, 29.05.1993 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 2♀, Geghard monastery, 15.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Arzakan environs, Aghveran recreation area, 22.07.1976 (A. Karapetian); 1♂, Garni, 8.06.1978 (M. Kalashian); 2♂, Kaputan, 40.3347°N / 44.6877°E, 1700 m, 30.07.2020 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: 1♀, Yervandashat, 3.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 1♀, Bagaran, 30.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 1♀, same locality, 40.1367°N, 43.6810°E, 1200 m, 31.05.2020 (T. Ghrejan); 3♀, Bagaran, near Akhuryan River, 5.05.1936 (H. Avetian).

Yerevan: 3♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♀, 18.03.1907, 1♀, 1.05.1908, 1♀, 11.04.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); Yerevan environs, 1♂, 23.04.1924, 1♀, 10.05.1924 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♂, 2♀, Jrvezh, 18.04.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♀, S environs of Arpi, 3.08.1993 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1♂, Shvanidzor, 16.09.1936 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Distribution. Everywhere in upland xerophytic landscapes.

Dendarus (Pandarinus) extensus (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Syunik Prov.: 1♀, Saravan, 24.07.1926 (G. Ismailov); 4♂, 1♀, Khustup Mt., 30.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, 2♀, W slope of Kaputdzukh Mt., 2500 m, 4.08.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2♂, Shurnukh, 6.08.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, ~5 km NE Kirs (Kitsk), 2500–3000 m, 14–20.06.2007 (A. Malkhasian).

Distribution (total and local). Georgia, Azerbaijan (western regions), Armenia, Eastern Turkey (Artvin and Kars provinces). Armenia: Armavir and Gegharkunik provinces [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Syunik Province. See Table 1 for general distribution of this species.

Tribe Opatrini Brullé, 1832

Subtribe Ammobiina Desbrochers des Loges, 1902

Protilamus fausti fausti (Reitter, 1890)

Material. Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Yeraskh, 6.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., Ararat town environs, salt marshes, 6.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Sis, 23.05.1962 (G. Avakian).

Distribution. Ararat Province.

Subtribe Opatrina Brullé, 1832

Gonocephalum costatum (Brullé, 1832), sensu lato

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Byurakan, 1450 m, 16.07.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Getamej, 9.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 4 ex., Arzni, 18.08.1928 (Atroschenko); 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 8.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian); N environs of Geghadir, 20.08.1997 (A. Malkhasian); 1 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, between 40.101°N / 44.633°E, 1160 m and 40.117°N / 44.634°E, 1350 m, 3.06.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Parakar, 1.06.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Yerevan: 31 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 14.05.1925 (unknown collector); 1 ex., same locality, 18.07.1980 (M. Kalashian); Jrvezh, 1 ex., 31.05.1948, 1 ex., 3.10.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., same locality, 3.06.1969 (E. Kachvorian); 9 ex., same locality, 7.03.1971 (A. Karapetian); 1 ex., same locality, 10.05.1974 (M. Marjanyan); Nubarashen, 1 ex., 22.06.1948, 3 ex., 3.03.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Notes. Differences between two subspecies, *G. costatum costatum* and *G. costatum rugulosum* (Küster, 1849), are unclear and the ranges of both subspecies are sympatric. As a result, we interpret here this taxon as *Gonocephalum costatum* sensu lato until further clarification of the status of these dubious subspecies.

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species from Yerevan only; it is distributed also in other provinces of central Armenia.

Gonocephalum granulatum pusillum (Fabricius, 1792)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Gyumri, 1–2.07.1940 (A. Nahapetian); 1 ex., Jajur, 25.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1 ex., W environs of Marmashen, 24.05.1992 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Panik environs, 40.6729°N / 43.9809°E, 1735 m, 9.05.2021 (I. Stepanyan).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 2 ex., Areguni, 17.07.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 2 ex., Sevan town, 12.07.1926 (Atroschenko); 2 ex., same locality, 10.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Gilli (former lake, now fields), 9.07.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 2.09.1939 (S. Dahl); 2 ex., Drakhtik, 10–16.07.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., same locality, 12.05.1930 (Kara-Mursa); same locality, 40.5542°N / 45.2222°E, 1950 m, 8.05.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejyan); Shorzha, 3 ex., 20.06.1928, 2 ex., 15.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Nshkhark, 12.06.1939 (G. Avakian); 1 ex., Martuni, 14.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., Sevan Peninsula, 7.05.1971 (A. Karapetian).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Ttujur, 10.08.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., between Antarut and Amberd fortress ruins, 24.09.1978 (R. Ghukasyan); 2 ex., NW environs of Yegvard, SE slope of Arailer Mt., between 40.3681°N / 44.4687°E, 1680 m and 40.3893°N / 44.4678°E, 2200 m, 29.05.1993 (M. Kalashian); S slope of Aragats Mt., near Amberd fortress ruins, 40.3886°N / 44.2256°E, 1 ex., 29.06.1999, 1 ex., 5.05.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 3 ex., Geghard monastery, 30.05.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 15.05.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1 ex., same locality, 17.05.1972 (A. Karapetian); 1 ex., W environs of Geghard monastery, 40.1389°N / 44.8112°E, 1750 m, 1 ex., 23.05.1999, 1 ex., 2.06.2001 (M. Kalashian); 3 ex., Garni, 30.05–1.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Garni environs, 40.1289°N / 44.6912°E, 1460 m, 25.04.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejyan); Gokht, 1 ex., 2.04.1941, 1 ex., 22.05.1941 (M. Ter-MinAsian); 2 ex., N environs of Geghadir, 20.08.1997 (A. Malkhasyan); 1 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, 40.0990°N / 44.6334°E, 1150 m, 1–2.05.2001 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., Kaputan, 40.3347°N / 44.6877°E, 1700 m, 30.07.2020 (M. Kalashian).

Armarvir Prov.: Parakar, 3 ex., 2.05.1925, 1 ex., 12.06.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Yervandashat, 3.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 9.10.1978 (R. Ghukasyan).

Yerevan: 23 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); Yerevan environs, 1 ex., 23.04.1924, 4 ex., 14.03.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Mushavan settl., 29.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Jrvezh, 31.05.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., Nubarashen, 19.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 2 ex., 27.04.1986, 2 ex., 21.04.1989 (M. Kalashian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Vedi, 2.05.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); Masis, 8 ex., 23–26.03.1962, 4 ex., 4–16.04.1962, 1 ex., 14.05.1962, 1 ex., 6.10.1962 (N. Akramowski); Nizami, 1 ex., 23.04.1962, 1 ex., 25.05.1962, 1 ex., 11.06.1962 (N. Akramowski); “Khosrov Forest” reserve, Vedi area, between 39.9791°N / 44.8792°E, 1300 m and 40.0081°N / 44.9096°E, 1560 m, 1 ex., 10.07.1992, 1 ex., 24.07.1992 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdзор Prov.: 2 ex., Martiros, 16.05.1953 (S. Vardikian); 1 ex., Saravan, 13.05.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Areni environs, Noravank gorge, 45.209°N / 39.701°E, 1220 m, 8.06.2000 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Gnishik, 27.05.2006 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., NE environs of Vayk, between 39.6946°N / 45.4974°E, 1505 m and 39.6890°N / 45.4941°E, 1320 m, 10.10.2014 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., S environs of Lichk, abandoned Boghakar vill., 1800 m, 2.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Goris, 15.05.1931 (L. Bekosipov); Meghri, 4 ex., 30.04.1938, 4 ex., 15.04.1939 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1 ex., same locality, 20.05.1938 (Marutian); 1 ex., Nerkin Hand environs, “Plane Grove” Sanctuary, 25.04.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Gorayk, 39.6874°N / 45.7141°E, 2340 m, 29.04.2021 (G. Karagyan).

Distribution. Everywhere in Armenia, except for mesophytic habitats.

Gonocephalum pubiferum Reitter, 1904

Material. Ararat Prov.: 2 ex., Abovyan vill. near Azat River, 28.05.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Vayotsdзор Prov.: 2 ex., Arpi, 20.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species only from Ararat Province (Goravan sands); new for Vayotsdзор Province.

Gonocephalum rusticum (Olivier, 1811)

Material. Yerevan: 11 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., same locality, 16.03.1904 (V. Dobrowljanskiy); 2 ex., Botanical Garden, 26.09.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Vedi, 2.05.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., Masis, 26.09.1973 (unknown collector); 1 ex., “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 18.08.1996 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., ~5 km N Dvin, Azat water-body, 40.0775°N / 44.6198°E, 1053 m, 24.06.2015 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., W environs of Dashtakar 39.9234°N / 44.7470°E, 960 m, at light, 18.08.2015 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan, G. Karagyan).

Syunik Prov.: 3 ex., Nrnadzor, 24.05.1948 (S. Vardikian).

Distribution. Central and southern Armenia.

Gonocephalum setulosum setulosum (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Armenia. Ararat Prov.: “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8929°N / 44.7343°E, 950 m, at light, 11.07.2018 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdзор Prov.: 1 ex., Arpi, 20.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Azerbaijan. Nachichevan AR: 3 ex., Djulfa, 29.04.1919 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Kizilvank, 6.05.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species for Aras valley without clear locality; new for Vayotsdзор Province of Armenia and for Nachichevan Autonomous Republic of Azerbaijan.

Opatroides punctulatus parvulus (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 4 ex., Gokht, 2.04.1941 (M. Ter-MinAsian); Armarvir Prov.: 8 ex., Sardapat (D. Maljushenco); Parakar, 1 ex., 30.03.1925, 2 ex., 7.04.1925, 6 ex., 25.06.1925, 1 ex., 11.08.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 2 ex., 6.07.1950, 2 ex., 19.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 5 ex., Jrrat environs, “Vordan karmir” Sanctuary, 40.0769°N / 44.2406°E, 940 m, 18.03.1997 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 6 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1 ex., 16.03.1908, 2 ex., 1.04.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskiy); 2 ex., same locality, 13.11.1939 (A. Richter); Nubarashen, 1 ex., 27.06.1948, 3 ex., 19.09.1948, 1 ex., 6.07.1950, 2 ex., 19.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., same locality, 3.06.1969 (E. Kachvorian); 5 ex., same locality, 7.03.1971 (A. Karapetian); N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 4 ex., 13.03.1984, 4 ex., 21.04.1987, 2 ex., 27.04.1996 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., same locality, 4.05.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Ararat town (D. Maljushenco); 8 ex., same locality, 25.04.1927 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); W environs of Dashtakar, 44.7470°N / 39.9234°E, 960 m, 3.06.2015 (M. Kalashian); 4 ex., same locality, 39.9230°N / 44.7472°E, 965 m, 31.03.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan); 1 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, Azat water body, 40.0816°N / 44.6287°E, 1060 m, 24.04.2021 (M. Kalashian); 5 ex., “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 960 m, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 25.04.2021 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., Surenavan environs, 39.8169°N / 44.7424°E, 810 m, 27.04.2021 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 39.7761°N / 44.8255°E, 970 m, 26.05.2021 (T. Ghrejyan); 2 ex., same locality, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan, M. Mazmanyan).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Karchevan, 29.06.1961 (G. Avakian).

Distribution. Distributed in central and southern Armenia.

Opatrum geminatum Brullé, 1832

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Jajur, 25.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1 ex., Panik environs, 40.6729°N / 43.9809°E, 1735 m, 9.05.2021 (I. Stepanyan).

Lori Prov.: Sanahin railway station, 23.04.1907 (D. Maljushenco).
Gegharkunik Prov.: 2 ex., Sevan Peninsula, 7.05.1971 (A. Karapetian); 1 ex., Drakhtik, 40.5542°N / 45.2222°E, 1950 m, 8.05.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian).

Araratotsn Prov.: 15 ex., Aruch (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Byurakan, 12–13.07.1948 (A. Richter); 2 ex., Karbi environs, 40.3473°N / 44.3458°E, 1320 m, 18.04.2021 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., W environs of Antarat, 40.3581°N / 44.2530°E, 1600 m, 26.04.2021 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., W environs of Agarak, 40.2964°N / 44.2706°E, 1100 m, 26.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 19 ex., Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., same locality, 13.08.1928 (unknown collector); 2 ex., Arzni, 14.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Geghard monastery, 30.05.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 31.05.1934 (G. Ismailov); same locality, 1 ex., 29.04.1941, 5 ex., 15.05.1949 (M. Ter-Minasian); same locality, 1 ex., 2.05.1950, 1 ex., 15.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 17.05.1971 (A. Karapetian); 1 ex., W environs of Geghard monastery, 40.1377°N / 44.8080°E, 1510 m, 25.04.2021 (T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan); Garni, 1 ex., 20.04.1928, 1 ex., 29.04.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., same locality, 1.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 2 ex., same locality, 40.1289°N / 44.6920°E, 1460 m, 19.05.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian); 2 ex., Gokht, 2.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian); 1 ex., N environs of Arzakani, 25.05.1975 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Kaputan, 40.3347°N / 44.6877°E, 1700 m, 30.07.2020 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Armavir town, 13.05.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Yerevan: 15 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 18.04.1909 (V. Dobrowlanskyi); Yerevan environs, 1 ex., 23.04.1924, 1 ex., 30.04.1927, 6 ex., 14.03.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Gardens near Getar River, 3.04.1925 (M. Ryabov); 1 ex., Jrvezh, 22.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian); 2 ex., Kanaker-Zeytun County, 4.07.1947 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 25.04.1971 (A. Karapetian); 1 ex., same locality, 23.04.1975 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 3 ex., W environs of Dashtakar, 44.7470°N / 39.9234°E, 960 m, 3.06.2015 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, Azat water body, 40.0816°N / 44.6287°E, 1060 m, 24.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdзор Prov.: 6 ex., NE environs of Vayk, between 39.6946°N / 45.4974°E, 1505 m and 39.6890°N / 45.4941°E, 1320 m, 10.10.2014 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Aras valley, Gegharkunik Province [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; actually distributed in majority of provinces of Armenia, so far not found in Tavush and Syunik provinces only.

Opatrum sabulosum sabulosum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Artik, 2.06.1934 (G. Ismailov); 7 ex., Amasia, 24–25.07.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Gyumri, 14.11.1937 (G. Avakian); 2 ex., Jajur, 25.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1 ex., W environs of Marmashen, 24.05.1992 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Goghovit, 18.07.2020 (M. Arakelyan); 1 ex., Panik environs, 40.6729°E 43.9809°N / 1735 m, 9.05.2021 (I. Stepanyan).

Lori Prov.: 1 ex., Vanadzor (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., Sanahin, 25.04.1907 (D. Maljushenco); 8 ex., same locality, 18.08.1937 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1 ex., Vahagni, 17.05.1922 (D. Maljushenco); 3 ex., Jrashen environs, 40.7329°N / 44.2164°E, 2090 m, 22.06.2020 (M. Kalashian).

Tavush Prov.: 2 ex., Dilijan, 11.06.1926 (G. Ismailov).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 4 ex., Sevan town (D. Maljushenco); 2 ex., same locality, 7.08.1925 (M. Rjabov); 8 ex., same locality, 9.06.1929 (Bockarev); same locality, 1 ex., 21.08.1926 and 10 ex., 15.06.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 1 ex., 2.09.1934 and 1 ex., 17.08.1952 (N. Akramowski); Sevan peninsula, 30.06.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., Vardenis, 31.07.1925 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Tsovagyugh, 12.07.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., 2–4 km NE Tsovagyugh, 2100–2400 m, 17.06.1988 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Tsovagyugh environs, 40.6407°N / 44.9629°E, 2095 m, 8.05.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian); 1 ex., Shorzha environs, 20.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 8 ex., Tsapatagh, 15.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 1 ex., 12.04.1930 and 1 ex., 4.06.1930 (Kara-Mursa); Drakhtik, 14 ex., 10.05.1930, 1 ex., 16.07.1927, 2 ex., 20–26.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 10 ex., 18.04.1930, 4 ex., 12.05.1930 (Kara-Mursa); same locality, 40.5542°N / 45.2222°E, 1950 m, 8.05.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejian); 2 ex., Chambarak environs, 2700 m, 11.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., 4–6 km S Madina, ~2400 m, 18.07.1991 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Gegharkunik vill., 40.2489°N / 45.1543°E, 2180 m, 16.05.2021 (T. Ghrejian, M. Mazmanyanyan, G. Karagyan); 1 ex., N environs of Semyonovka, 40.6730°N / 44.8990°E, 2280 m, 15.05.2021 (T. Ghrejian, M. Mazmanyanyan, G. Karagyan).

Araratotsn Prov.: 2 ex., Ttujur, 10.08.1930 (unknown collector); 2 ex., NW environs of Tsaghkahovit, soil traps, 29.06–17.07.1998 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 3 ex., Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Arzni, 14.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Hankavan, 20.08.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Gokht, 2.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian).

Armavir Prov.: 15 ex., Yervandashat, 26.04.1936 (Shcherbakova); same locality, 7 ex., 3.05.1936, 1 ex., 29.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 8 ex., Hushakert, 28.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 3 ex., Bagaran, 30.04–6.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Baghramyanyan environs, 40.1819°N / 43.8441°E, 1055 m, 6.03.2021 (T. Ghrejian).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Yerevan, 14.04.1904 (V. Dobrowlanskyi); Yerevan environs, 4 ex., 18.04.1929, 3 ex., 30.03.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Hrazdan River valley, 19.04.1925 (M. Rjabov); 4 ex., Jrvezh, 22.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian).

Ararat Prov.: 3 ex., Ararat town (D. Maljushenco). 3 ex., Masis, 17.03.1962 (Yeghiazarian).

Vayotsdзор Prov.: 1 ex., Martiros, 17.05.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Syunik Prov.: 2 ex., Kajaran, 9.08.1927 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., same locality, 24.04.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., NW environs of Vardandzor, abandoned Lichkvaz vill., 26.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 3 ex., Kapudjukh Mt., 3000 m, 28.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Meghri, 30.04.1938 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 2 ex., same locality, 6.06.1938 (Matutian); 1 ex., Kajaran, Kapudjukh Mt., 2700 m, 6.06.1980 (N. Khazhakyanyan); 1 ex., Gorayk, 39.6874°N / 45.7141°E, 2340 m, 29.04.2021 (G. Karagyan).

Distribution. Everywhere in Armenia.

Penthicus (Discotus) dilectans (Faldermann, 1836)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Zvartnots vill. environs, Zvartnots Cathedral ruins, 7.11.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 3 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 19.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. Goravan sands (Ararat Province) according to Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011]; new for Armavir Province.

Penthicus iners (Ménétriés, 1832)

Material. Syunik Prov.: S environs of Lichk, abandoned Boghakar vill., 1800 m, 1 ex., 21.06.1929, 1 ex., 2.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., W slope of Kapudzhukh Mt., 2500 m, 7.08.1957 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species was listed from “Armenia: Arax” by Reichardt [1936]; known only from southern Armenia.

Penthicus rufescens rufescens (Mulsant et Rey, 1859)

Material. Armavir Prov.: Parakar, 2 ex., 5.06.1925, 2 ex., 25.06.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); steppe near Echmiadzin, 3 ex., 5.06.1925, 1 ex., 5.04.1935, 1 ex., 6.07.1935, 16 ex., 8–10.08.1935, 2 ex., 19.10.1935 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 8.06.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 19.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Echmiadzin, 25.06.1954 (I. Ioannissian); 3 ex., Zvartnots vill. environs, Zvartnots Cathedral ruins, 1.06.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: 3 ex., Nubarashen, 27.04.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Zoo, 31.07.1957 (S. Vardikian).

Ararat Prov.: 4 ex., Urts Mt. near Armash, 9.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1 ex., 23.06.1993, 2 ex., 20.07.2014 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., ~4 km NE Tigranashen, 39.806°N / 44.971°E, 1680 m, 29.06.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. South-western Armenia.

Scleropatroides brevisculus (Reitter, 1889)

Material. Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Meghri, near Aras River, 23.04.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species is known only from Syunik Province.

Scleropatroides hirtulus (Baudi di Selve, 1876)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 21.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian);

Ararat Prov.: 5 ex., Yeraskh, 6.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species was listed for Ararat railway station [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Armavir Province.

Scleropatroides seidlitzii (Reitter, 1898)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Parakar, 17.07.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Distribution. South-western Armenia. The species was recorded for Armenia in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020] without locality data.

Tribe Pedinini Eschscholtz, 1829
Subtribe Leichenina Mulsant, 1854
Leichenium mucronatum Küster, 1849

Material. Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., 3 km NE Shvanidzor, 27–28.03.2003 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Goravan sands [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for southern Armenia.

Subtribe Pedinina Eschscholtz, 1829
Pedinus femoralis femoralis (Linnaeus, 1767)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 3♂, Artik, 2–3.08.1934 (G. Ismailov); 2♂, Ashotsk (D. Maljushenco); 1♂, Amasia, 9.08.1938 (G. Avakian); 1♀, Jajur, 25.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1♀, Gyumri, 10.05.1951 (unknown collector); 1♂, near Arpi Lake, 7.08.1991 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, W environs of Marmashen, 24.05.1992 (M. Kalashian); 2♂, 2♀, 2 km SE Arpi Lake, 7.08.1992 (M. Kalashian); 2♂, Vahramaberd environs, 18–20.03.1999 (M. Kalashian).

Lori Prov.: 2♂, 1♀, Spitak (D. Maljushenco); 1♀, Stepanavan environs, Medvezh'ya Mt., 18.08.1920 (unknown collector); 1♀, Akhtala environs, 15.08.1932 (unknown collector).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1♀, Gavar, 31.07.1925 (G. Ismailov); 2♂, 1♀, Sevan town, 7.08.1925 (M. Ryabov); 1♀, same locality, 5.06.1929 (Bochkarev); Shorzha environs, 1♀, 20.06.1928, 1♂, 15.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 1♀, Tsapatagh, 15.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♂, 2♀, Drakhtik, 10–20.04.1930 (Kara-Mursa); 1♀, Nshkhark, 14.06.1939 (G. Avakian); 1 ex., Lchashen, 19.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Kotayk Prov.: 2♂, Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♀, 29.07.1907, 1♀, 1♂, 21.06.1908 (V. Dobrowljanskyi).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♀, Tutujur, 10.08.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, N slope of Aragats Mt., 2400 m, 15.15.1975 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, between Antarat and Amberd fortress ruins, 18.06.1978 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 1♂, 3♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♀, 2.03.1906, 1♀, 20.03.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskyi).

Distribution. Widely distributed in Armenia.

Pedinus strabonis Seidlitz, 1893

Material. Shirak Prov.: 2♂, Ashotsk (D. Maljushenco); 5♂, 1♀, Gyumri (D. Maljushenco); 15♂, same locality, 18–23.04.1919 (unknown collector); 4♂, 3♀, Artik, 2.08.1934 (G. Ismailov).

Lori Prov.: 2♂, 1♀, Spitak (D. Maljushenco).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1♂, Sevan Lake, railway station near Sevan Peninsula, 8.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♂, Antarat, 2.06.1935 (unknown collector).

Kotayk Prov.: 1♀, Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 1♀, Getamej, 2.06.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, N environs of Geghadir, 20.08.1997 (A. Malkhasian); 1♂, W environs of Voghjaberd, 40.1754°N / 44.6324°E, 1635 m, 16.04.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 2♂, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); Nubarashen, 1♂, 27.06.1948, 1♂, 1♀, 24.04.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Jrvezh, 31.05.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, same locality, 26.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species only from Gegharkunik Province; it is distributed also in Yerevan, Shirak, Lori, Aragatsotn, and Kotayk provinces.

Subfamily Tenebrioninae Latreille, 1802
Tribe Alphitobiini Reitter, 1917
Alphitobius diaperinus (Panzer, 1796)

Material. Lori Prov.: 1 ex., S environs of Gargar, Pushkin Pass, 25.07.1991 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 4 ex., Yerevan, 1.05.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); same locality, 40.1979°N / 44.4915°E, 1090 m, 1 ex., 25.06.2011, 1 ex., 24.11.2015, 2 ex., 31.07.2020 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Arabkir County, 2.11.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Nubarashen, 24.04.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2 ex., Botanical garden, 17.06.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Arabkir park, 40.2100°N / 44.4982°E, 1140 m, 10.07.2014, on *Ulmus* sp. (G. Karagyan).

Distribution. The species is distributed in woody habitats of Armenia in western and northern parts of the country.

Diaclina testudinea (Piller et Mitterpacher, 1783)

Material. Lori Prov.: 1 ex., Vahagni, 8.07.1920 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia);

Yerevan: 1 ex., Yerevan, 13.11.1939 (A. Richter); 2 ex., same locality, 13.06.1979 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Kanaker vill., 15.04.1908 (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., Botanical garden, 23.07.1984 (A. Karapetyan).

Armavir Prov.: 3 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 27.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan);

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Shikahogh, 5.08.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., same locality, 21.04.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Karmrakar, 17.06.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); Meghri, 29.05.1975 (M. Marjanyan).

Distribution. Widespread in all territory of the country with woodlands.

Tribe Bolitophagini W. Kirby, 1837
Bolitophagus reticulatus (Linnaeus, 1767)

Material. Tavush Prov.: 1♂, Kirants, 16.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, Sevkar environs, 41.0045°N / 45.1721°E, 672 m, at light, 23.08.1915 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghredjyan, G. Karagyan).

Distribution. Khznorian [1957] listed this species from Ijevan, Sevkar and Zangezur. Widespread in forests of Armenia.

Eledona agricola (Herbst, 1783)

Material. Syunik Prov.: 3 ex., Shurnukh, 4–5.08.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Tsav, light trap, 1.07.1970 (S. Pustovarov).

Distribution. The species was recorded from Shurnukh and Sevkar [Khznorian, 1957]; distributed in Tavush and Syunik provinces.

Eledonoprius serrifrons (Reitter, 1890)

Material. Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Sraschen, 27.06.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species is known from Syunik Province.

Tribe Dissonomini Medvedev, 1968
Dissonomus picipes (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Gokht, 2.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian); 1 ex., Garni environs, 8.06.1978 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., same locality, 40.1289°N / 44.6912°E, 1460 m, 25.04.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejyan); 1 ex., Geghadir environs, 10.05.1997 (K. Yeranyan); 2 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, 40.1176°N / 44.6347°E, 1350 m, 25.06.2000 (M. Kalashian); 3 ex., Kaputan, 40.3347°N / 44.6877°E, 1700 m, 30.07.2020 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: 3 ex., Parakar, 7–12.04.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Parakar environs, 24.04.1926 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 11 ex., Taronik, 8.06.1925 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 5 ex., Aknalich village environs, Akna Lich Lake, 8.06.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., steppe near Echmiadzin, 15.04.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); Yervandashat, 2 ex., 23.04.1936, 6 ex., 3.05.1936, 8 ex., 27.06.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Hushakert, 28.04.1936 (H. Avetian); Bagaran, 4 ex., 30.04.1936, 7 ex., 6.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Arax railway station, 21.04.2001 (G. Karagyan).

Yerevan: 13 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); Yerevan environs, 10 ex., 23.04.1924, 1 ex., 10.05.1924, 10 ex., 21.06.1924 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex.,

same locality, 25.06.1988 (I. Ioannissian); 1 ex., Hrazdan River valley, 12–18.04.1925 (M. Rjabov); 2 ex., Jrvezh, 11.04.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); Nubarashen, 2 ex., 24.04.1949, 4 ex., 7.05.1952, 1 ex., 16.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., same locality, 3.06.1969 (E. Kachvorian); N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 2 ex., 21.04.1989, 4 ex., 21.04.1993 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., same locality, 4.05.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Ararat town environs, 25.04.1927 (unknown collector); 2 ex., "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 15.06.1979 (M. Kalashian); 3 ex., same locality, 25.04.2021 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Goravan vill. environs, 39.8846°N / 44.7335°E, 1000 m, 19.04.2021 (T. Ghrejyan); 3 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, Azat water body, 40.0816°N / 44.6287°E, 1060 m, 24.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 3 ex., Shatin, 16.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 4 ex., Yeghegnadzor, near Arpa River, 20.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., NW environs of Vernashen, 29.04.1978 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Meghri, 15.09.1946 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Shvanidzor, 2.06.1989 (G. Arakelian).

Distribution. Widely distributed in mountain steppes and subdeserts of Armenia.

Tribe Helopini Latreille, 1802
Subtribe Cylindrinotina Español, 1956
Armenohelops armeniacus Nabozhenko, 2002

See type material in Nabozhenko [2002a].

Material. Gegharkunik Prov.: 2♂, 7♀, Shorzha, 20.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Araratsothn Prov.: 1♀, Aparan, highway, 1600 m, 30.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, E environs of Artashavan, S slope of Arailer Mt. between 40.3835°N / 44.4285°E, 1750 m and 40.4037°N / 44.4360°E, 2440 m, 19.05.1996 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1♀, Geghard monastery, 8.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasian); 1♂, same locality, 2.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, SW environs of Gokht, Havuts Tar Monastery ruins, 10.04.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, Bjni, 27.06.1957 (S. Vardikian).

Yerevan: 1♂, Hrazdan River gorge, 25.04.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Kanaker-Zeytun County, 22.06.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: "Khosrov Forest" reserve, Vedi area, between 40.0057°N / 44.9090°E, 1550 m and 40.0243°N / 44.9095°E, 1850 m, 1♂, 30.04.1982, 1♀, 25.06.1992, 1♀, 24.05.1999 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 3♂, 1♀, Jermuk, 17.04.1975 (E. Herthetvzian); 1♀, Gnishik environs, 31.05.2002 (M. Kalashian).

Note. Included into the Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia [Kalashyan, 2010c].

Distribution. The species was described and further reported [Nabozhenko, 2002a; Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011] from Kotayk, Yerevan and Ararat provinces; new for Vayotsdzor and Gegharkunik provinces.

Cylindrinotus erivanus (Reitter, 1902)

Material. 1♂, Lusagyugh, 30.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); Araratsothn Prov.: 1♂, Aparan, lake, 31.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian);

See other material in the revision of Nabozhenko [2015].

Notes. Included into the Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia [Kalashyan, 2010d].

Distribution. Central and western Armenia.

Cylindrinotus femoratus (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 2♂, 3♀, 2–4 km N Ashotsk, 8–9.06.1994 (M. Kalashian).

Tavush Prov.: 1♂, Getahovit, 23.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Kirants, 1.06.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Yenokavan environs, Lastiver Campground, 40.9032°N / 45.0610°E, 1130 m, 26.06.1986 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, NW environs of Teghut vill., 40.7875°N / 44.9162°E, 1190 m, soil traps, 12–25.06.2005 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, E environs of Kozman, "Zikatar" Sanctuary, 41.1263°N / 44.9200°E, 1270 m, 27.04.2016 (M. Kalashian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: Drakhtik, 1♂, 15.06.1923, 1♀, 23.06.1923 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, same locality, 2.05.1930 (Kara-Mursa); 1♂, 3♀, Tsapatagh, 15.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Sevan town, 5.06.1929 (Bochkarev); 1♂, same locality, 10.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, same locality, 5.09.1932 (N. Akramowski); 1♂, Nshkhark, 11.06.1939 (G. Avakian); 1♀, Lchashen, 18.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Tsovaguyugh, 2900 m, 29.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 4♂, Sevan Lake, Sevan Peninsula, 7.05.1971 (A. Karapetian); 1♂, Sotk environs, 40.2090°N / 45.9258°E, 6.06.2009 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Ttujur environs, 40.6514°N / 45.2958°E, 1740 m, 12.05.2016 (M. Kalashian); 2♀, NW environs of Aghberk, 40.5458°N / 45.2714°E, 2100 m, 12.05.2016 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, W environs of Tsovaguyugh, 40.6360°N / 44.9267°E, 2030 m, 14.05.2016 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, 1♀, Gegharkunik vill. environs, 40.2488°N / 45.1542°E, 2190 m, 1.05.2018 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Tsovaguyugh environs, 40.6381°N / 44.9250°E, 1960 m, 9.05.2021 (G. Karagyan, T. Ghrejyan); 1♂, 1♀, N environs of Semyonovka, 40.6730°N / 44.8990°E, 2280 m, 15.05.2021 (T. Ghrejyan, M. Mazmanyanyan, G. Karagyan).

Araratsothn Prov.: 1♂, N environs of Tsilkar, 40.7299°N / 44.1964°E, 2170 m, 28.04.2018 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejyan).

Kotayk Prov.: 6♂, 8♀, Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 8♂, 1♀, Hrazdan town (D. Maljushenco); 6♂, same locality, 4.06.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskiy); 1♀, Fantan, Mt. Ketan-dag, 2.06.1936 (G. Ismailov); 1♂, same locality, forest, 8.06.1959 (G. Avakian); 1♀, same locality, 5.05.1975 (M. Marjanyan); 1♀, same locality, 1800 m, 19.05.2013 (V. Martirosyan).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, Armash environs, 10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 2♀, Gnishik, 20.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, Martiros, 2400 m, 18.10.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, Elpin, 17.06.1956 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, N environs of Vernashen, 1.05.1985 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, 1♀, N environs of Ughedzor, 39.6954°N / 45.6818°E, 1970 m, 2.05.2013 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 4♂, 6♀, Gorayk, 13.05.1931 (L. Bekosipov); 1♂, 1♀, Shurnukh, 13.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, Karmrakar, 17.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, 1♀, Chakaten, 26–27.06.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, ~3 km N Artsvanik, 39.3263°N / 46.4733°E, 1410 m, soil traps, 10.04–14.05.2008 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Shishkert environs, 39.0629°N / 46.3668°E, 1400 m, 16.05.2008 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Sev Lich Lake environs, 39.5932°N / 46.2871°E, 2575 m, 18.06.2020 (T. Ghrejyan, G. Karagyan).

See also material in the revision of Nabozhenko [2015].

Distribution. Widespread in Armenia.

Cylindrinotus gibbicollis Faldermann, 1837

Material. Sirak Prov.: 48♂, 36♀, Ashotsk (D. Maljushenco); 2♂, 1♀, same locality, 2000–2300 m, 23.06.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Shaghrik, 12.07.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1♂, Ghazanchi, 12.07.1934 (G. Ismailov).

Lori Prov.: 3♀, Privolnoye, 2.05.1922 (unknown collector); 1♀, Vahagni, 2.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2♂, Vanadzor (D. Maljushenco); 1♀, same locality, forest, 30.06.1949 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Tavush Prov.: 1♀, Ijevan, forest, 10.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2♂, E environs of Ijevan, Skhtorut Mt, 2000 m, 8–10.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Kirants, 15.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1♀, Tsapatagh, 15.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, 5♀, Nshkhark, 10–12.06.1939 (G. Avakian); 2♀, Aghberk environs, Ayrija Mt., 24.07.1939 (G. Avakian); 1♀, Vaghashen, 30.07.1939 (G. Avakian); 1♂, NW environs of Aghberk, 40.5458°N / 45.2714°E, 2100 m, 12.05.2016 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, N environs of Semyonovka, 40.6730°N / 44.8990°E, 2280 m, 15.05.2021 (T. Ghrejyan, M. Mazmanyanyan, G. Karagyan).

Araratsothn Prov.: 2♂, Tsilkar environs near Spitak Pass, 2700 m, 31.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1♂, 1♀, Tsaghkadzor; 7.06.1907 (D. Maljushenco); 1♂, 1♀, NW environs of Yegvard, SE slope of Arailer Mt., between 40.3681°N / 44.4687°E, 1680 m and 40.3893°N / 44.4678°E, 2200 m, 23.05.1985 (M. Kalashian).

See also material in the revision of Nabozhenko [2015].

Distribution. All territory of Armenia excluding southern part, meadows.

Ectromopsis bogatschevi (Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1957)

Type material. 1♀, holotype, with the Cyrillic label: "Ереван, Советашен, АССР, 15.4.53" (Yerevan, Sovetashen [= Nubarashen], Armenian SSR, 15.4.[19]53 [leg. S. Iablokoff-Khznorian]) and with additional labels: "typus (Iablokoff-Khznorian hand)", "*Helops bogatschevi* Khnz." (Iablokoff-Khznorian hand) and "Holotypus, *Helops bogatschevi* Khznorian, 1957, M. Kalashian det., 2021" (printed on red paper); 1♂, 2♀, paratypes,

with the same data, but 24.04.1949; 1 ex. with label "Kaukasus, Kanakiry [= Kanaker, Cyrillic script], Maluschenco [leg.]"; 1♀, paratype from Nubarashen is deposited in ZIN.

Material. Yerevan: Nubarashen, 2♂, 1♀, 10.04.1952, 1♀, 2.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 1♂, 1♀, 13.03.1984, 2♂, 1♀, 21.04.1993, 2♂, 5♀, 21.04.1999 (M. Kalashian).

Notes. Included into the Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia [Kalashian, 2010e].

Distribution. The species occurs only in south-western Armenia (Yerevan, Nubarashen), on clayey soils.

Eustenomacidius (Caucasohelops) svetlanae araxi
Nabozhenko, 2006

Material. Vayotsdzor: 1♀, Vernashen environs, 10.05.1985 (M. Kalashian).

Distributed. Only one this locality of the species in Armenia, on rocks.

Nalassus (Caucasonotus) diteras (Allard, 1876)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1♂, Ashotsk, 2500 m, 27.06.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1♂, 2♀, Sevan Lake, Sevan Peninsula, 30.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion).

Kotayk Prov.: 2♂, 2♀, Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 1♂, same locality, 5.05.1975 (M. Marjanyan); Tsaghkadzor environs, Alibek Mt., 4.06.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); E environs of Artavaz vill., camp of Yerevan State University, 1♂, 2♀, 5–15.06.1983, 1♂, 1♀, 15.07.1988, 1♀, 2.07.1994 (M. Kalashian); 2♂, Hankavan, 40.6364°N / 44.5014°E, 1990 m, 26.06.2016 (G. Karagyan).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] reported this species for Gegharkunik Province only; new for Shirak and Kotayk provinces.

Nalassus faldermanni (Faldermann, 1837)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 6♂, Ashotsk (D. Maljushenco); W environs of Marmashen, 1♂, 15.06.1980, 2♂, 24.05.1992 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, Panik environs, 40.6729°N / 43.9809°E, 1735 m, 9.05.2021 (I. Stepanyan).

Lori Prov.: 1♀, Gargar (D. Maljushenco); 1♀, Shamlugh, 10.08.1922 (unknown collector).

Tavush Prov.: 1♀, Ijevan, forest, 10.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 1♀, 2–3 km W Ijevan, 25.06.1980 (M. Kalashian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 2♂, Varsar, 17.06.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); Sevan town, 1♀, 15.06.1928, 3♂, 1♀, 10.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♀, same locality, 5.06.1929 (Bochkarev); 4♂, 1♀, Drakhtik, 19.04.1930 (Karamursa); 7♂, 1♀, Shorzha environs, 15.05.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Lchashen, 18.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 2♂, Sevan Peninsula, 7.05.1971 (A. Karapetian); 1♂, Artanish, 13.06.1982 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, Gegharkunik vill., 40.2489°N / 45.1543°E, 2180 m, 16.05.2021 (T. Ghrejian, M. Mazmanyan, G. Karagyan).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♂, Talin (D. Maljushenco); 2♂, Karbi environs, 40.3473°N / 44.3458°E, 1320 m, 18.04.2021 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 2♂, 1♀, Tsaghkadzor (D. Maljushenco); 13♂, 7♀, Arzni, 14.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Garni, 20.04.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2♂, Gokht, 2.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasion); 2♂, 1♀, Geghard monastery, 29.04.1941 (M. Ter-Minasion); 1♂, same locality, 18.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 2♂, same locality, 28.03.1977 (M. Kalashian); 2♂, Garni, Azat River gorge, 17.07.1985 (A. Karapetian); 1♀, Dsoragyugh, 1–2.04.1994 (A. Sukiasyan); 1♂, Kaputan, 6.05.1997 (K. Yeranyan); 2♀, Geghadir environs, 8.04.2001 (K. Aghababayan); S environs of Hatsavan, 40.0990°N / 44.6334°E, 1150 m, 3♂, 1♀, 2.05.2001, 1♂, 1♀, 3.06.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Armarvir Prov.: 1♂, 1♀, Lukashin environs, 16.05.1928 (M. Makarian); steppe near Echmiadzin, 1♂, 10.04.1930, 2♂, 6♀, 20.04.1930 (unknown collector); 1♀, Echmiadzin, 13.04.1983 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Yervandashat, 3.05.1936 (H. Avetian).

Yerevan: 14♂, 5♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♂, 1♀, 16.05.1908, 2♂, 21.05.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 22♂, same locality, 13–26.04.1941 (M. Aloyan); 1♀, hills up to Hrazdan River, 2.04.1922 (unknown collector); Yerevan environs, 1♂, 2♀, 23.04.1924, 1♂, 14.03.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 10♂, 1♀, Yerevan environs, stony desert, 11.04.1935

(unknown collector); 2♂, Jrvezh, 15.04.1945 (A. Richter); 1♂, same data (H. Terterian); 1♀, same data (A. Oghanjanian); same locality, 1♂, 22.04.1941, 2♂, 26.04.1945 (M. Ter-Minasion); same locality, 2♂, 1♀, 16.05.1948, 1♂, 27.04.1975 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 1♂, same locality, 26.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan); 1♀, Nork County, 3.07.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 1♂, 1♀, Tsitsernakaberd park, 28.03.1977 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Kanaker-Zeytun County, 40.2089°N / 44.5366°E, 1250 m, 6.04.2021 (T. Ghrejian).

Ararat Prov.: 7♂, 1♀, Agamzalu, 23.03.1926 (unknown collector); 2♂, 2♀, "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 28.03.2001 (K. Aghababian); "Khosrov Forest" Reserve, Vedi area, between 39.9791°N / 44.8792°E, 1300 m and 40.0081°N / 44.9096°E, 1560 m, 2♀, 6–7.07.2003, 1♂, 2♀, 17.05.2005, 1♂, 1♀, 2–4.06.2006 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♂, 3♀, ~4 km N Vernashen, 29.04.1978 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Shatin, 8.05.1979 (M. Kalashian); 2♀, Gnishik environs, 11.05.1998 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, Areni environs, 16.05.1998 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: Meghri, 1♂, 8.05.1937, 2♀, 30.04.1938 (M. Ter-Grigorian); 1♀, NNE environs of Meghri, Kaladash Mt., 18.05.1958 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 1♂, Shamb, 20–26.06.1941 (H. Avetian); 1♂, Shurnukh 14.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 1♀, 1 km N Shurnukh, 12.06.2007 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, Srashen, 23.04.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, 2–3 km W Tsav, 23.04.1988 (M. Kalashian); 2♂, 2♀, between Tsav and Srashen, 39.0539°N / 46.4899°E, 1050 m, 16.05.2008 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, 3–5 km W Kajaran, 1800–2000 m, 23.07.1999 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, E Lichk, 39.05°N / 46.19°E, 1650 m, 18.06.2000 (K. Aghababian); 3♀, Vank, 39.04°N / 46.23°E, 1860 m, 15.06.2003 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, 2 km N Karmrakar, 39.33°N / 46.46°E, 1290 m, on Crataegus sp., 12.06.2007 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Widely distributed and numerous species in Armenia.

Odocnemis allardi Nabozhenko et Keskin, 2016

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♀, NW environs of Yegvard, SE slope of Arailer Mt., between 40.3681°N / 44.4687°E, 1680 m and 40.3893°N / 44.4678°E, 2200 m, 23.05.1985 (M. Kalashian); S slope of Aragats Mt., near Amberd fortress ruins, 1♂, 3♀, ~2500 m, 5.05.1991, 1♀, 40.4060°N / 44.2275°E, 2200 m, 22.05.2014 (M. Kalashian); S environs of Yernjatap, Arailer Mt., 40.4030°N / 44.4591°E, 2530 m, 6.07.2020 (T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan).

Armarvir Prov.: 1♂, Karakert, 19.05.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, N environs of Paruyr Sevak, Urts Mt., 2440 m, 25.05.1958 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion).

See also the large type series in the revision [Nabozhenko, Keskin, 2016].

Distribution. High mountains of western Armenia; feed on epilithic parmelian lichens.

Odocnemis aurichalcea (Adams, 1817)

Material. Lori Prov.: Teghut mine, Dukanadzor gorge, 41.0910°N / 44.8514°E, 890 m, soil traps, 2♂, 4♀, 1–24.05.2014, 1♂, 2♀, 29.04–25.05.2016 (M. Kalashian) and 3♂, 29.04–25.06.2017 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan); 1♂, 27.04–21.05.2018 (T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan).

Tavush Prov.: 2 ex., Kozman, 11–16.06.1953 (M. Ter-Grigorian).

Distribution. Forests of northern Armenia.

Zophohelops humeridens (Reitter, 1902)

Material. Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♀, E Sers, Gogi Mt., 3000 m, 1.07.1935 (unknown collector); 1♂, same locality, 7.06.1958 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion).

Syunik Prov.: 2♀, Khustup Mt., 30.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorion); 1♂, Kajaran, abandoned Atkiz vill., 2500 m, 6.06.1954 (N. Akramowski); Meghri pass, 39.1161°N / 46.1607°E, 2540 m, 2♂, 5.06.1993, 1♀, 14.05.2008 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Alpine meadows in southern Armenia.

Subtribe Helopina Latreille, 1802

Adelphinus (Adelphinops) ordubadensis Reitter, 1890

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 1♂, 6 km N Kanch, 27.06.2004 (M. Kalashian).

Kotayk Prov.: 2♂, S environs of Hatsavan, 1200–1400 m, 29.06.1997 (A. Malkhasyan); 2♂, 1♀, 4 km S Hatsavan, 40.0952°N / 44.6342°E, 1150 m, 14.06.2006 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: 1♂, Parakar environs, 4.06.1952 (G. Avakian); 1♀, Jrarat, "Vordan Karmir" Sanctuary, 40.0769°N / 44.2406°E, 940 m, 29.05.2017 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, Ptghunk environs, 40.1747°N / 44.3733°E, 930 m, 23.06.2017 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 2♂, 1♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♀, 24.03.1908, 1♂, 1.04.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); Jrvezh, 2♀, 1.06.1948, 1♂, 15.06.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2♀, "Erebuni" Reserve, 40.1441°N / 44.6142°E, 1300 m, 20.06.2010 (K. Yeranyan).

Ararat Prov.: "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1♀, 9.06.1993, 1♂, 1♀, 1.06.2006, 1♀, 1.06.2014 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, N environs of Dashtakar, 39.9279°N / 44.7613°E, 1000 m, 3.06.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♂, Areni environs, Noravank gorge, 45.209°N / 39.701°E, 1220 m, 8.06.2000 (M. Kalashian).

Note. Included into the Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia [Kalashyan, 2010f].

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species for Aras valley without locality data; new for Vayotsdzor Province; often on Tamarix sp.

Catomus antoniae Reitter, 1890

Material. Armavir Prov.: 2♀, Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 19.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: 1♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco).

Distribution. This rare species is fragmentary distributed in Armenia: Echmiadzin (Armavir Province), Yeghegnadzor District (Vayotsdzor Province) and Meghri District (Syunik Province) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011].

Entomogonus (Delonurops) amandanus (Reitter, 1902)

Type material. *Hedyphanes corax* Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1957: 1♂, holotype, with the Cyrillic label "Мергри, Каладаш, СССР, 6.5.54" (Meghri, Armenian SSR, Kaladash [canyon E of] Meghri, 6.5.[19]54 [leg. S. Iablokoff-Khznorian]), as well as with labels: "Typ. *Hedyphanes corax* Khznorian det." and "Holotypus, *Hedyphanes corax* Khznorian, 1957, M. Kalashian det., 2021" (printed on red paper). Synonymy by Nabozhenko [2002b].

Material. Syunik Prov.: 1♂, NW environs of Vardanidzor, abandoned Lichkavaz vill., 18.07.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Tkhhut, 25.05.1943 (H. Avetian); 1♀, ~2 km W Tkhhut, 38.985°N / 46.185°E, ~1300 m, 13.05.2000 (K. Aghababian); 1♂, ~4 km N Shvanidzor, 10.06.2007 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, ~5 km N Shvanidzor, 38.98°N / 46.37°E, ~1400 m, 16.06.2008 (M. Kalashian).

Note. Included into the Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia [Kalashyan, 2010g].

Distribution. This rare species is endemic for southern Armenia (Syunik Province).

Entomogonus (Delonurops) clavimanus Reitter, 1903

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 1♀, Geghadir 19.04.1953 (unknown collector); 1♂, Garni, 16.04.1978 (M. Kalashian); 4♂, 2♀, S environs of Hatsavan, 40.0990°N / 44.6334°E, 1150 m, 1.05.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 14♂, 14♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); same locality, 1♀, 14.04.1906, 1♀, 18.04.1907, 4♂, 1♀, 22–24.04.1908, 1♀, 12.04.1909, 1♀, 16.04.1909, 1♀, 21.04.1910, 1♀, 24.04.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1♂, same locality, 18.05.1938 (M. Ter-Minasian); 1♂, Yerevan, gardens, 10–11.05.1933 (Asisian); 1♀, Jrvezh, 15.04.1945 (A. Richter); same locality, 1♂, 11.04.1948, 1♂, 16.05.1948, 2♀, 24.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2♂, same locality, 25.04.1971 (A. Karapetian); Nubarashen, 1♂, 1♀, 17.04.1952, 1♀, 19.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 2♂, same locality, 13.04.1969 (E. Kachvorian); N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 2♂, 31.03.1988, 1♀, 21.04.1993, 2♂, 2♀, 29.04.1997 (M. Kalashian); 4♀, same locality, 4.05.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, Ararat town environs, 25.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); "Khosrov Forest" reserve, 1♂, 6.06.1986 (K. Yeranyan); 1♂, same locality, between 39.9791°N / 44.8792°E, 1300 m and 40.0081°N / 44.9096°E, 1560 m, 2–4.06.2006 (M. Kalashian); 4♂, 2♀, E environs of Bardzrashen, Azat water body, 40.066°N / 44.617°E, 1070 m, 3.05.2001 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, NE environs of Urtsadzor, 39.932°N / 44.818°E, 1100 m, 17.04.2008 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, W environs of Dashtakar, 44.7470°N / 39.9234°E,

960 m, 10.04.2018 (T. Ghrejian, A. Saribekyan); 1♀, Urtsadzor environs, 39.9084°N / 44.8887°E, 11.04.2021 (N. Zariqyan).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♂, Rind, 31.05.1979 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1♀, Pukhrut, 39.1307°N / 46.2205°E, 2130 m, 25.05.2005 (G. Karagyan).

Distribution. Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed this species for central Armenia without locality data; new for Vayotsdzor and Syunik provinces.

Euboeus (Pelorinus) medvedevi Abdurakhmanov et Nabozhenko, 2011

Note. This species is known only by holotype from Alaverdi (Lori Province) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]. Schneider and Leder [1878] probably also recorded *E. medvedevi* under the name "*Helops subrugosus* Duft." from Armenia.

Euboeus (Pelorinus) sp.

Material. Syunik Prov.: 3♂, 1♀, Meghri, 30–31.05.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1♀, same locality, 24.05.1945 (H. Avetian); 1♂, Chakaten, 25.05.1942 (H. Avetian); 1♂, S environs of Lichk, abandoned Nor Arevik vill., 26.04.1943 (H. Avetian); 2♂, 1♀, same locality, 5.05.1954 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, Vahravar, 27.05.1945 (H. Avetian); 1♂, Tsav, 21.07.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♀, Srashen, 23.06.1981 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, 4–6 km N Shvanidzor, 20.04.2001 (K. Aghababian); 1♀, Pukhrut, 39.1307°N / 46.2205°E, 2130 m, 25.05.2005 (G. Karagyan); 1♂, 1♀, E environs of Kapan, Geghanush, 39.2221°N / 46.4240°E, 1030 m, soil traps, 8.04–14.05.2008 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, N environs of Kapan, Ghatar locality, 39.2206°N / 46.3880°E, 1120 m, soil traps, 8.04–14.05.2008 (M. Kalashian); 1♀, S environs of Lichk, 39.0336°N / 46.1932°E, 1700 m, 8.05.2016 (M. Kalashian); N Shvanidzor vill., 38.9851°N / 46.3746°E, 1320 m, 1♂, 9.06–8.08.2017, 1♂, 2♀, 16.06–26.08.2018, soil traps (T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan).

Notes. Bogatshev [1938b] was the first, who interpreted this species, known only from southern Armenia and Nakhichevan as *Probatiscus vicinus* (Allard, 1876). However, this species differs from *Euboeus vicinus*, and it is a new taxon, which will be described in a separate taxonomic revision.

Hedyphanes laticollis Fischer von Waldheim in Ménétrés, 1832

Material. Syunik Prov.: 1♂, Sarnakunk, 21.05.1998 (M. Kalashian).

Notes. The species was erroneously listed for Armenia [Iwan et al., 2020] without confirmation of any material. In fact, this specimen is the first record for Armenia.

Hedyphanes mannerheimi Faldermann, 1837

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 1♀, Geghard monastery, 31.05.1934 (G. Ismailov).

Armavir Prov.: 1♂, Parakar, 16.04.1925 (M. Rjabov); same locality, 3♂, 1♀, 2–9.05.1925, 1♂, 24.04.1926 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Yervandashat, 23.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 1♀, Bagaran, near Akhuryan River, 5.05.1936 (H. Avetian); 4♂, 2♀, Echmiadzin, 2.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, Zvartnots vill. environs, Zvartnots Cathedral ruins, 1.06.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: Yerevan, 1♂, 4.04.1907, 2♂, 20.04.1907, 2♂, 14.04.1908, 1♀, 16.04.1909 (V. Dobrowljanskyi); 1♂, 14♀, same locality (D. Maljushenco); 1♂, Yerevan, 28.04.1977 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, Nubarashen, 19.04.1953 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); N environs of Nubarashen, 40.0957°N / 44.5433°E, 1100 m, 1♂, 1.04.1984, 1♂, 23.01.2001 (M. Kalashian); 3♂, 3♀, same locality, 4.05.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian).

Ararat Prov.: 6♂, 1♀, Ararat town environs, 25.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, Urts Mt. near Armash, 30.04.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♀, "Goravan sands" Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 940 m, 1♂, 11.06.1979, 1♂, 20.06.1990 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, same locality, 28.03.2001 (K. Aghababian); 1♀, Kaghtrashen vill., S slope of Odzasar Mt.,

1.06.1997 (A. Malkhasian); 1♂, “Khosrov Forest” Reserve, W border of Vedi area, 39.9766°N / 44.8740°E, 1310 m, 4–8.06.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1♂, Areni, 12.05.1953 (S. Vardikian).

Distribution. Yerevan, Ararat, Vayotsdzor and Syunik provinces [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Kotayk Province. Xerophytic steppes, subdeserts.

Hedyphanes tagenioides Faldermann, 1832

Material. Armavir Prov.: 1♀, Parakar, 17.04.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, Hushakert, 28.04.1936 (H. Avetian); 3♀, Echmiadzin, 2.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1♂, 1♀, Arax railway station, 21.04.2001 (G. Karagyan); 1♂, NW environs of Khanjan, 40.2067°N / 43.9884°E, 924 m, 4.05.2013 (M. Kalashian); 5♂, 1♀, Baghramyan environs, 40.1779°N / 43.8389°E, 1070 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan); 1♂, Artamet environs, 40.1519°N / 43.8734°E, 1005 m, 7.04.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, G. Karagyan, M. Mazmanyan).

Yerevan: 13♂, 1♀, Yerevan (D. Maljushenko); same locality, 1♂, 9.04.1909, 1♀, 18.04.1909, 1♂, 16.04.1910, 1♀, 21.04.1910 (V. Dobrowljanskiy); 4♂, Yerevan environs, 11.04.1935 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1♂, hills up to Hrazdan River, 2.04.1922 (unknown collector).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 15.06.1997 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Central and western Armenia; xerophytic steppes, subdeserts.

Tribe Melanimonini Seidlitz, 1894

Cheirodes sardous sardous Gené, 1839

Material. Armavir Prov.: 2 ex., Parakar, 18.05.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); same locality, 2 ex., 5.05.1925, 1 ex., 31.05.1925, 28 ex., 22–28.06.1925, 1 ex., 16.07.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 3 ex., Taronik, 5.07.1925 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 2 ex., Zvartnots vill. environs, Zvartnots Cathedral ruins, 1.06.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenko); 1 ex., same locality, 25.05.1928 (G. Ismailov).

Ararat Prov.: 8 ex., Ararat town, 24.06.1928 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., Asni ruins, 28.06.1933 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 3 ex., Mrgavet, at light, 10.07.1956 (local collectors); “Goravan sands” Sanctuary, 960 m, 39.8932°N / 44.7335°E, 8 ex., 15.06.2004, 2 ex., 15–16.06.2013, at light (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., ~5 km N Dvin, Azat water body, 40.0775°N / 44.6198°E, 1053 m, at light, 24.06.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 2 ex., Areni environs, Noravank monastery, 39.6878°N / 45.2217°E, 1350 m, at light, 27–28.06.2016 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 4 ex., Meghri, 15.05.1958 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., E Meghri, Artsvakar canyon, 38.9115°N / 46.2728°E, 670 m, at light, 28–29.06.2003 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Southern and western Armenia.

Cheirodes (Pseudanemia) brevicollis Wollaston, 1864

Material. Yerevan: 1 ex., Yerevan environs (A. Schelkovnikov).

Ararat Prov.: 2 ex., Mrgavet, at light, 10.07.1956 (local collectors); 4 ex., ~5 km N Dvin, Azat water body, 40.0775°N / 44.6198°E, 1053 m, at light, 24–25.06.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Armavir Province [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Yerevan and Ararat provinces. The species is omitted for Armenia and Azerbaijan in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020].

Tribe Palorini Matthews, 2003

Palorus orientalis Fleischer, 1900

Material. Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., Arpi, 3.08.1983 (M. Kalashian).

Note. New for Armenia. The species was known only from Talysh Mts. (Azerbaijan).

Palorus ratzeburgii (Wissmann, 1848)

Material. Armenia. Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Tsav, 22.04.1981 (M. Kalashian).

Azerbaijan (Nakhichevan AR): 2 ex., Ordubad environs, 28–29.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species was known in Armenia from Ijevan (Tavush Province) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Syunik Province of Armenia and Nakhichevan of Azerbaijan.

Tribe Scaurini Billberg, 1820

Scaurus araxinus Richter, 1945

Material. Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Armash environs, Asni ruins, 39.7960°N / 44.8415°E, 1200 m, at light, 8.08.2021 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejian, M. Mazmanyan).

Distribution. Armenia (Ararat Province), Azerbaijan (Nakhichevan) [Nabozhenko et al., 2018].

Tribe Tenebrionini Latreille, 1802

Neatus subaequalis Reitter, 1920

Material. Lori Prov.: 1 ex., Sanahin, 17.08.1937 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 2 ex., Teghut mine, 41.0915°N / 44.8506°E, 930 m, 24.03.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 1 ex., Kanaker vill., 15.04.1908 (D. Maljushenko); 2 ex., Jrvezh, 10.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species is known from Yerevan and northern Armenia.

Tenebrio angustus Zoufal, 1892

Material. Ararat: 2 ex., Artashat, 20.07–15.08.2015 (local collectors).

Note. New for Armenia.

Tenebrio molitor Linnaeus, 1758

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., S slope of Aragats Mt., 3–5 km NNE Antarat, 29.05.1983 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., S slope of Aragats Mt., Amberd fortress ruins, 40.3970°N / 44.2262°E, 2210 m, 2.06.2000 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. This cosmopolitan species is widespread in Armenia, but specimens are usually not collected; Armenia is omitted in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020].

Tenebrio obscurus Fabricius, 1792

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Anushavan, 40.6317°N / 43.9972°E, 1855 m 19.07.2020 (M. Arakelyan).

Lori Prov.: 3 ex., Stepanavan, 28.05.1922 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Vanadzor, 17.07.1949 (L. Tovmasian).

Tavush Prov.: 3 ex., Koghb (D. Maljushenko); 1 ex., Ijevan, forest, 10.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Byurakan, 29.05.1983 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., NW environs of Yegvard, SE slope of Arailer Mt., between 40.3681°N / 44.4687°E, 1680 m and 40.3893°N / 44.4678°E, 2200 m, 23.05.1985 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: Sardarapat, 19.05.1928 (M. Makarian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., S environs of Garni, abandoned Alakre vill., 11.06.1997 (A. Malkhasyan); 1 ex., S environs of Hatsavan, 40.0990°N / 44.6334°E, 1–2.05.2001 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenko); 1 ex., same locality, 22.05.1928 (Atroschenko); 1 ex., Yerevan, gardens, 20–29.05.1933 (Asisian); 1 ex., Yerevan environs, 7.07.1924 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., same locality, 18.06.1934 (F. Sosnin); 1 ex., Kanaker-Zeytun County, 10.06.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Armash, 10.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Yeraskh, 12.06.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Shurnukh, 17.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 4 ex., Meghri, gardens, 4.06.1957 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Khndzoresk, 1300 m, 19.06.1996 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. This cosmopolitan species is widespread in Armenia, but the country is omitted in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020].

Tribe Toxicini Oken, 1843*Cryphaeus cornutus* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1823)

Material. Lori Prov.: 1♀, Vahagni, 8.07.1920 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 4♀, Sanahin, 18.07.1937 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1♀, Akhtala, 4.09.1983 (M. Kalashian).

Tavush Prov.: 1♀, Koghb, 30.07.1928 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 2♂, Getahovit, 12.06.1938 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1♀, Dilijan, sanatorium, 19.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1♂, Dilijan, 11.07.1973 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., N environs of Tegut vill., Haghartsin monastery, 40.8043°N / 44.8895°E, 1550 m, 2.07.2005 (M. Kalashian); 1♂, E environs of Ditavan, 40.9745°N / 45.2129°E, 850 m, soil traps, 30.06–15.09.2015 (T. Ghrejan).

Ararat Prov.: 1♀, W environs of Dashtakar, 39.9234°N / 44.7470°E, 960 m, 18.08.2015, at light (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan, G. Karagyan);

Syunik Prov.: 2♂, 1♀, Tsav, 29.07.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Distribution. The species is widely distributed in woodlands of the country. It was listed from Dilijan and Tsav [Khnzorian, 1957].

Tribe Triboliini Gistel, 1848*Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst, 1797)

Material. Lori Prov.: 2 ex., Spitak Distr., borrow of *Spalax* sp., 1979 (unknown collector).

Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Jrrat, "Vordan karmir" Sanctuary, 40.0652°N / 44.1250°E, 853 m, 13.06.2017 (G. Karagyan).

Yerevan: Yerevan, 1 ex., 22.09.1949, 1 ex., 11.11.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., same locality, in flour, 25.03.1972 (G. Avakian); Botanical garden, 1 ex., 30.05.1950, 2 ex., 5.07.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Ararat Prov.: 2 ex., ~5 km N Dvin, Azat water-body, 40.0775°N / 44.6198°E, 1053 m, at light, 24.06.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Widespread in Armenia, but entomologists usually don't collect this cosmopolitan store pest.

Tribolium confusum Jacquelin du Val, 1861

Material. Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Abovyan town, 27.05.1925 (M. Rjabov). Yerevan: 1 ex., Yerevan (D. Maljushenco); 1 ex., same locality, 17.08.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., same locality, 25.03.1972 (G. Avakian); 4 ex., same locality, 23.12.1972 (H. Avetian); 1 ex., Jrvezh, 7.05.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Distribution. Widespread in Armenia, but entomologists usually don't collect this cosmopolitan store pest.

Tribolium madens (Charpentier, 1825)

Material. Aragatsotn Prov.: 2 ex., Ashtarak, 5.05.1964 (G. Avakian). Armavir Prov.: 2 ex., Bagaran, 4.05.1936 (H. Avetian). Yerevan: 1 ex., Jrvezh, 16.05.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., Kanaker-Zeytun County, 20.05.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Distribution. Widespread in Armenia, but entomologists usually don't collect this cosmopolitan store pest.

Subfamily Diaperinae Latreille, 1802**Tribe Crypticini Brullé, 1832***Crypticus quisquilius quisquilius* (Linnaeus, 1761)

Material. Shirak Prov.: 1 ex., Shaghrik, 12.07.1934 (G. Ismailov); 1 ex., Ghazanchi, 12.07.1934 (G. Ismailov); 2 ex., Amasia, 28.07.1934 (G. Ismailov); 2 ex., Artik, 2.08.1934 (G. Ismailov).

Tavush Prov.: 1 ex., Dilijan, 3.07.1926 (G. Ismailov).

Gegharkunik Prov.: 1 ex., Sevan Lake, Sevan Peninsula, 4.07.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 2 ex., Sevan Lake, railway station near Sevan Peninsula, 8.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., Areguni environs, 17.07.1923 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 3 ex., Sevan town, shore of Sevan Lake, 7–9.08.1925 (M. Rjabov); 1 ex., Sevan town, 29.07.1926

(Atroschenko); same locality, 1 ex., 15.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); same locality, 1 ex., 2.09.1934 (N. Akramowski); Sevan town environs, 1 ex., 25.07.1982, 1 ex., 3.08.1982 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., Varsar, 17.06.1927 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Shorzha, 20.06.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Tsapatagh, 18.07.1928 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Tsovinar, 7.07.1935 (A. Bagdasarian); 2 ex., Lchashen, 18.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1 ex., 2–4 km NE Tsovagyugh, 17.06.1988 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., 4–6 km S Madina, ~2400 m, 18.07.1991 (M. Kalashian).

Aragatsotn Prov.: 1 ex., Ttujur environs, 3.08.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Apnagayugh environs, Gegharot River, 2600 m, 3.08.1930 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Aragats Mt., Karilich Lake, 3200 m, 25.08.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 2 ex., NW environs of Tsaghkavovit vill., soil traps, 29.06–17.07.1998 (M. Kalashian).

Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Aknalich vill., Akna Lich Lake, 8.06.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Hankavan, 2150 m, 1.08.1924 (Expedition of Museum of Armenia); 1 ex., Tsaghkadzor, 2.07.1994 (M. Kalashian); 2 ex., ~1.5 km W Artavaz, 15.07.2012 (local collectors).

Yerevan: 4 ex., Yerevan, 20.04.1907 (V. Dobrowljanskyi).

Vayotsdzor Prov.: 1 ex., E environs of Gndevaz, Mt. Amulsar, 39.7269°N / 45.7152°E, 2980 m, soil traps, 13.06–4.09.2018 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Noravan environs, 39.5454°N / 46.0937°E, 1865 m, 22.08.2020 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan).

Distribution. Widespread in Armenia on meadows.

Tribe Diaperini Latreille, 1802**Subtribe Adelinina LeConte, 1862***Alphitophagus bifasciatus* (Say, 1824)

Material. Ararat Prov.: 2 ex., Zovashen, 23.02.1977 (E. Harutyunian).

Syunik Prov.: 3 ex., Nerkin Hand environs, "Plane Grove" Sanctuary, 21.07.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 4 ex., same locality, 6.07.1981 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Known from western and southern Armenia.

Subtribe Diaperini Latreille, 1802*Diaperis boleti* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material. Lori Province: 1 ex., Stepanavan, on birch, 2.05.1904 (N. Safarian); 4 ex., Shagali, 8.07.1920 (unknown collector); 1 ex., Teghut mine, artificial pond, 41.0907°N / 44.8117°E, 950 m, at light, 23.07.2015 (M. Kalashian).

Gegharkunik Prov.: Aygut, 40.6783°N / 45.1850°E, 1400 m, 1.07.2016 (T. Ghredjian).

Kotayk Prov.: 1 ex., Hrazdan town (D. Maljushenco); Tsaghkadzor, 20.07.1910 (D. Maljushenco).

Yerevan: Yerevan gardens, 20–29.05.1933 (Asisian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Karmrakar, 17.06.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Distribution. Widespread in Armenia, in gardens and forests.

Neomida quadricornis (Motschulsky, 1873)

Material. Tavush Prov.: 1 ex., Yenokavan environs, Lastiver Campground, 40.9032°N / 45.0610°E, 1130 m, 26.06.1986 (M. Kalashian); Aygehovit, 2♂, 2♀, 15.08.1985, 4♂, 2♀, 15.07.1996 (M. Kalashian).

Yerevan: 1♂, 1♀, Yerevan, 15.09.2009 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1♂, Nerkin Hand environs, "Plane Grove" Sanctuary, 21.07.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian); 1♂, 1♀, Shurnukh, 3.08.1952 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Distribution. This species was recorded for Shuknukh and Tsav (Syunik Province) under the name "*Haplocephala haemorrhoidalis* F" [Khnzorian, 1957]; new for Tavush Province and Yerevan.

Pentaphyllus testaceus (Hellwig, 1792)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 9 ex., Aknalich vill. environs, Akna Lich Lake, 27.04.1975 (M. Marjanyan).

Yerevan: 2 ex., Jrvezh, 27.04.1975 (S. Iablokoff-Khnzorian).

Note. New for Armenia and Transcaucasia.

Pentaphyllus chrysomeloides (Rossi, 1792)

Material. Yerevan: Zoo, 5.06.1942 (A. Richter); 4 ex., Kanaker-Zeytun County, 1.05.1958 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Shikahogh, 6.07.1981 (A. Karapetian).

Distribution. Tavush Province (Ijevan, Dilizhan) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for central and southern Armenia.

Platydemia tristis Laporte et Brullé, 1831

Material. Lori Prov.: 2 ex., Vahagni, 2.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Tavush Prov.: 1 ex., N environs of Teghut vill., Haghartsin monastery, 5.10.1975 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., Yenokavan environs, Lastiver Campground, 40.9032°N / 45.0610°E, 1130 m, 26.06.1986 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., ~5 km S Noyemberyan, 18.08.1988 (M. Kalashian); 4 ex., between Haghartsin vill. and Parzlich Lake, 40.7561°N / 44.9630°E, 1350 m, 3.06.2005 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Shurnukh, 10.08.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov); 3 ex., same locality, 9.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. Widespread in leaf forest of Armenia.

Platydemia violacea (Fabricius, 1790)

Material. Lori Prov.: 2 ex., Sanahin, 17.08.1937 (Expedition of Institute of Zoology of Armenia); 1 ex., Teghut mine, near refuse heap, 41.0725°N / 44.8394°E, 1180 m, soil traps, 22.05–29.06.2018 (T. Ghrejan, G. Karagyan).

Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Shurnukh, 14.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. The species is known from forests of northern and southern Armenia [Khznorian, 1957]

Tribe Hypophlaeini Billberg, 1820*Corticeus bicolor* (Olivier, 1790)

Material. Tavush Prov.: 2 ex., Kirants, 14–15.05.1951 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); N environs of Teghut vill., Haghartsin monastery, 2 ex., 10.05.1975, 1 ex., 1.05.1977 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. Tavush Province ([Khznorian, 1957], present data).

Corticeus basalis Reitter, 1884

Material. Syunik Prov.: 2 ex., Shurnukh, 11–12.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Chakaten, 22.04.1981 (M. Kalashian); 3 ex., Kapan, Vahanavank monastery ruins, 24.04.1981 (M. Kalashian).

Distribution. The species was known from Syunik Province [Khznorian, 1957].

Corticeus longulus (Gyllenhal, 1827)

Material. Lori Prov.: 1 ex., Vanadzor, Shagali, 2.06.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian); 1 ex., Vahagni, 2.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Tavush Prov.: 1 ex., Dilijan, sanatorium, 19.05.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Note. New for Armenia and Transcaucasia.

Corticeus suberis (Lucas, 1846)

Material. Syunik Prov.: Srashen, 5.07.1981 (A. Karapetyan).

Note. New for Armenia and Transcaucasia.

Corticeus unicolor Piller et Mitterpacher, 1783

Material. Lori Prov.: 1 ex., Akhtala, 31.08.1925 (A. Schelkovnikov); 1 ex., Shamlugh, 12.08.1932 (A. Schelkovnikov); 5 ex., Alaverdsi Distr., 24.08.1932 (A. Schelkovnikov); 2 ex., Vahagni, 2.06.1949 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Tavush Prov.: 3 ex., Yenokavan environs, Lastiver Campground, 40.9032°N / 45.0610°E, 1130 m, 26.06.1980 (M. Kalashian).

Syunik Prov.: 3 ex., Shikahogh, 5.08.1929 (A. Schelkovnikov).

Distribution. Widespread in forests of northern and southern Armenia.

Tribe Myrmechixenini Jacquelin du Val, 1858*Myrmechixenus picinus* (Aubé, 1850)

Material. Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., “Khosrov Forest” Reserve, Vedi area, 39.9791°N / 44.8792°E, 1300 m, 23.05.1990 (M. Kalashian).

Note. New for Armenia and Transcaucasia.

Myrmechixenus subterraneus Chevrolat, 1835

Note. This species was recorded for Armenia by Nikitsky [2011] based on his material.

Tribe Phaleriini Blanchard, 1845*Phthora hauseriana* (Reitter, 1895)

Material. Armavir Prov.: 1 ex., Jrarat environs, “Vordan karmir” Sanctuary, 840 m, 40.0762°N / 44.2405°E, 18.03.1988 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., same locality, 4.05.1990 (A. Sukiasyan).

Distribution. Armavir Province.

Phthora plagiocnema (Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1956)

Type material. 1 ex., holotype of *Phthora plagiocnema* (Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1956) with the Cyrillic label: “Епeван, cr. Апар, АССР, 15.05.54” (Yerevan, Ararat station, Armenian SSR [leg. S. Iablokoff-Khznorian]) and with additional labels: “typus” (Iablokoff-Khznorian’ hand), “*Cataphronetis plagiocnema* Khnz.” (Iablokoff-Khznorian’ hand) and “Holotypus, *Cataphronetis plagiocnema* Khznorian, 1956, M. Kalashian det., 2021” (printed on red paper). 9 ex., paratypes, with the same locality data.

Material. Ararat Prov.: 1 ex., Mrgavet, at light, 10.07.1956 (local collectors).

Distribution. The species is known only from Ararat Province of Armenia.

Tribe Scaphidemiini Reitter, 1922*Scaphidema metallica metallica* (Fabricius, 1792)

Material. Lori Prov.: 2 ex., Teghut mine, near refuse heap, 41.0743°N / 44.8399°E, 1105 m, soil traps, 20.06–1.08.2013 (M. Kalashian); 1 ex., 41.0705°N / 44.8378°E, 1210 m, 23.07–23.09.2015 (M. Kalashian, G. Karagyan); 1 ex., same mine, near arteficial pond, 41.0907°N / 44.8117°E, 990 m, soil traps, 22.07–25.08.2016 (M. Kalashian, T. Ghrejan); 41.0725°N / 44.8394°E, 2 ex., 22.05–29.06.2018, 1 ex., 29.06–20.08.2018 (T. Ghrejan, G. Karagyan).

Kotayk Prov.: 3 ex., Tsaghkadzor, 10.07.1948 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian). Syunik Prov.: 1 ex., Shurnukh, 14.06.1950 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Distribution. Tavush Province (Ijevan, Dilijan) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]; new for Lori, Kotayk and Syunik provinces.

Species, excluded from the fauna of Armenia in the present paper**Subfamily Pimeliinae Latreille, 1802****Tribe Cnemeplatiini Jacquelin du Val, 1861***Cnemeplatia atropos* A. Costa, 1847

Material. Azerbaijan: 1 ex., Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic, Chananab, 29.04.1955 (S. Iablokoff-Khznorian).

Local distribution. Azerbaijan (Absheron, Gobustan, Talysh). New record for Nakhichevan Autonomous

Republic. We cannot support the record from Armenia (Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] listed it for Echmiadzin) by the material. So, we exclude this species from the faunistic list of Armenia until further confirmation.

Philhammus cribratellus (Reitter, 1901)

Note. The species was erroneously listed for southern Armenia [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011] after the monograph of Reichardt [1936], who incorrectly wrote “Armenia: Ordubad” for the locality of *P. cribratellus*. The species is known only from Ordubad (Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic, Azerbaijan) and has never been collected from other countries. So, we exclude this species from the faunistic list of Armenia.

Tribe Lachnogyini Seidlitz, 1894

Lachnogyia squamosa Ménériés, 1849

Notes. The species was listed for “Araxesthal” (Aras valley, ? Nakhichevan, Azerbaijan) by Reitter [1904] and for Vedi (Armenia) by Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011]. The last record is based on unpublished diaries of A. Bogatshev, but not supported by material. We exclude this species from the faunistic list of Armenia until further confirmation.

Tribe Leptodini Lacordaire, 1859

Leptodes (Mesoleptodes) lederi Reitter, 1889

Notes. The type locality of this species is “Araxesthal” (valley of the Aras River) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]. Leder collected this and many other species from “Araxesthal” on the territory of modern Armenia and Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic (Azerbaijan); therefore, the species was listed for Armenia and Nakhichevan by Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011]. Unfortunately, we did not find *L. lederi* in Armenia after the original description.

Tribe Pimeliini Latreille, 1802

Sternoplax (Pachysternoplax) armeniaca
(Faldermann, 1837)
(Fig. 5)

Material. 1 ex. (ZIN), “Armenia”, “*planiuscula* Motsch. Armen”.

Notes. This species is known by a series of specimens from HNHM and ZIN labelled as “Caucasus Araxesthal Leder Reitter” and also from Ordubad and Julfa (Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic, Azerbaijan). Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011] recorded this species for Armenia based on the mentioned above specimen, but this label can be interpreted as Armenia sensu lato. Bogatshev [1938a, b] two times published that this species occurs only in a small area in the Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic and has never been collected in Armenia. He also mentioned that one specimen from Leninakan (now Gyumri) environs is deposited in National Museum Georgia (Tbilisi); however, “this label, written in the illiterate hand of a person I know, is undoubtedly false” [Bogatshev, 1938b: 139]. Nobody collected these large and

Fig. 5. *Sternoplax (Pachysternoplax) armeniaca*, habitus (HNHM).
Рис. 5. *Sternoplax (Pachysternoplax) armeniaca*, рабiтyс (HNHM).

mobile beetles in Armenia, and we exclude it from the faunistic list of the country.

Tribe Lagriinae Latreille, 1825

Tribe Lagriini Latreille, 1825

Lagria atripes Mulsant et Guillebeau, 1855

Notes. This species was listed for Armenia [Iwan et al., 2020], but we did not collect it in Armenia and didn't find it in available collections. We exclude this species from the faunistic list of Armenia until further confirmation.

Subfamily Blaptinae Leach, 1815

Tribe Blaptini Leach, 1815

Blaps scabriuscula scabriuscula Ménériés, 1832

Notes. This species is distributed only in the Greater Caucasus on south to Gobustan desert. Bogatshev [1958] erroneously interpreted *Blaps puella* as a subspecies of *Blaps scabriuscula* and recorded this species under the name “*Blaps scabriuscula puella*” for Armenia.

The first author of this paper erroneously determined the large specimen of *Blaps kovali* from Ptichya cave as *B. scabriuscula* [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011]. Thus, the species must be excluded from the faunistic list of Armenia.

Neopachypterina Bouchard, Löbl et Merkl, 2007

Neopachypterus serrulatus (Reitter, 1904)

Notes. This species was listed for Armenia, Aras valley [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011] based on specimens from HNHM with the label "Caucasus Araxesthal Leder, Reitter". We cannot confirm this record by actual material with distinct localities in Armenia. Thus, the species is excluded from the faunistic list of Armenia.

Tribe Opatrina Brullé, 1832

Subtribe Opatrina Brullé, 1832

Opatrum verrucosum Germar, 1817

Notes. The species was listed from Alexandrapol (now Gyumri, Armenia) by Schneider and Leder [1878] but was not collected since that time. The record needs confirmation.

Penthicus pinguis pinguis Faldermann, 1836

Notes. Reichardt [1936] recorded this species for Armenia (Aras valley). Nobody collected this species in Armenia. At least we did not find material in ZIN and HNHM. The record needs confirmation.

Subtribe Sclerina Lacordaire, 1859

Sclerum carinatum Baudi di Selve, 1875

Notes. This species was collected from Armenia (without a distinct locality) by Schneider and recorded for the country under the name "*Scleron orientale* F." [Schneider, Leder, 1878]. Nobody has collected this species in this country since that time. The record needs confirmation.

Tribe Pedinini Eschscholtz, 1829

Subtribe Leichenina Mulsant, 1854

Leichenum canaliculatum canaliculatum (Fabricius, 1798)

Notes. This species was listed for Armenia, Aras valley [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011] based on specimens from HNHM with the label "Caucasus Araxesthal Leder, Reitter". We cannot confirm this record by actual material with distinct localities in Armenia. Thus, the species is excluded from the faunistic list of Armenia. On the other hand, this well-flying psammophilic species known from the Balkans, Transcaucasia and Central Asia can be found in Armenia in future.

Subfamily Tenebrioninae Latreille, 1802

Tribe Helopini Latreille, 1802

Subtribe Helopina Latreille, 1802

Helops caeruleus stevenii Krynicki, 1834

Notes. Schneider and Leder [1878] were the first authors who recorded this subspecies from northern

Armenia (Alexandrapol – now Gyumri). Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011], following these authors, listed *H. caeruleus stevenii* for the forest regions of northern Armenia. However, additional material has not supported this information for over 140 years. Therefore, we exclude it from the faunistic list of Armenia until confirmation.

Tribe Ulomini Blanchard, 1845

Uloma culinaris (Linnaeus, 1758)

Notes. This widespread and common species was listed for all countries of the Caucasus [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011], but for some reason, it is still not found in Armenia. Therefore, we exclude it from the faunistic list of Armenia until confirmation.

In addition to mentioned excluded species, we present corrections to the Catalogue of Palearctic Coleoptera [Iwan et al., 2020] (Table 1). Most parts of taxonomic and distributional corrections were made previously [Medvedev, 1968; Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011], and part of them was published in the recent revision of S. Chigray and Abakumov [2019].

Conclusion

In total, 123 species of Tenebrionidae, excluding Alleculinae, are reliably known from Armenia and confirmed by material, including seven species recorded for this country for the first time, one synonymized taxon and two undescribed species. Fourteen species were excluded from the faunistic list of Armenia because they are not confirmed by collection material; most of these taxa occur in adjacent territories and can potentially be found in Armenia in future. Four species are recorded for the Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic of Azerbaijan for the first time, and four species are new for the fauna of Transcaucasia. Fifteen species were excluded from the fauna of Armenia or synonymized in previous works, but this information has not been corrected in the Catalogue of the Palearctic Coleoptera [Iwan et al., 2020]. We again published correct distribution and synonymy. Most of these erroneous data are related to old unconfirmed and incorrectly determined material or old records of taxa for the former territory of Armenia within the Russian Empire (now these territories are the part of Turkey; partly modern Kars, Erzurum, Igdir, Ağrı and Van provinces).

Comb-clawed beetles (Tenebrionidae: Alleculinae) are presented by 31 species in the fauna of Armenia [Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1983]. All these species are confirmed by collection material in the mentioned monograph. This number may increase slightly, but not up to 50 species, as indicated in the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020].

Among species new to the fauna of Armenia, *Tenebrio angustus* can be attributed to invaders. This record is related to human activities because the species is noted as a pest of cereals, and it inhabits only synanthropic habitats [Denisova, 1940]. *Palorus orientalis* was known only from relic Hyrcan forests of Talysh and north Iran around the Caspian Sea and never was registered as a synanthropic

Table 1. Corrections to the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020] (taxa are given in order of mention in the Catalogue).
 Таблица 1. Исправления к каталогу [Iwan et al., 2020] (таксоны даны в том же порядке, что и в каталоге).

Species or nomenclatural act / Вид или номенклатурный акт	In Catalogue В каталоге	Correction Исправление	Author(s) of publication, comments Автор(ы) публикации, комментарии
<i>Laena bogatschevi</i> Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1984	valid species валидный вид	<i>Laena lederi</i> Weise, 1878 = = <i>Laena bogatschevi</i> (junior synonym / младший синоним)	Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko [2011: 280]
<i>Adesmia devecchii</i> Osculati, 1844	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent in Armenia отсутствует в Армении	Only one species, <i>A. maillei</i> , occurs in Armenia ([Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011], present data) / Только один вид, <i>A. maillei</i> , встречается в Армении ([Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011], настоящие данные)
<i>Pimelia dubia dubia</i> Faldermann, 1837	valid species валидный вид	<i>Pimelia cursor</i> Ménétrés, 1832 = = <i>Pimelia dubia</i> (junior synonym / младший синоним)	Bogatshev [1938b] established this synonymy; later Bogatshev [1953] interpreted <i>P. dubia</i> as a valid species; Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011: 204] resurrected this synonymy / Эту синонимию установил Богачёв [1938b]; позже [1953] он интерпретировал <i>P. dubia</i> как валидный вид; Абдурахманов и Набоженко [2011: 204] восстановили эту синонимию
<i>Pimelia schoenherri</i> Faldermann, 1837	valid species валидный вид	<i>Pimelia capito</i> Krynicki, 1832 = = <i>Pimelia schoenherri</i> (junior synonym / младший синоним)	Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko [2011: 203]
<i>Pimelia robusta</i> Kraatz, 1865	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent in Armenia / отсутствует в Армении	Excluded from the faunistic list of Armenia by Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011: 312] / Исключен из чек-листа Армении Абдурахмановым и Набоженко [2011: 312]
<i>Calyptopsis harpaloides</i> Baudi di Selve, 1874	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent in Armenia / отсутствует в Армении	Excluded from the Caucasian faunistic list by Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011: 311]; occurs only in north Iran [S. Chigray, Abakumov, 2019: 233] / Исключен из чек-листа Кавказа Абдурахмановым и Набоженко [2011: 312]; встречается только в Северном Иране [S. Chigray, Abakumov, 2019: 233]
<i>Calyptopsis nitescens</i> Reitter, 1897	occurs only in Armenia / встречается только в Армении	occurs only in SE Azerbaijan (Talysh) / встречается только в Юго-Восточном Азербайджане (Талыш)	Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko [2011: 178]
<i>Calyptopsis rosti</i> Reitter, 1897	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent on the Caucasus / отсутствует на Кавказе	The species is known only from north Iran [S. Chigray, Abakumov, 2019] / Вид известен только из Северного Ирана [S. Chigray, Abakumov, 2019]
<i>Dailognatha quadricollis carceli</i> Solier, 1835	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent on the Caucasus / отсутствует на Кавказе	Excluded from the Caucasian faunistic list by Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011: 310] / Исключен из чек-листа Армении Абдурахмановым и Набоженко [2011: 310]
<i>Microdera transversicollis</i> Reitter, 1887	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent on the Caucasus / отсутствует на Кавказе	<i>M. transversicollis</i> is erroneously mentioned for the Caucasus after the Reitter's taxon, described from Baku: <i>Microdera transversicollis</i> Reitter var. <i>parvicollis</i> Reitter, 1897 (junior homonym; valid name <i>M. reitteri</i> Kaszab, 1966) / <i>M. transversicollis</i> ошибочно упомянут для Кавказа начиная с таксона <i>Microdera transversicollis</i> Reitter var. <i>parvicollis</i> Reitter, 1897, описанного из Баку (младший синоним; валидное название <i>M. reitteri</i>)

Table 1 (continuation).
Таблица 1 (продолжение).

Species or nomenclatural act / Вид или номенклатурный акт	In Catalogue В каталоге	Correction Исправление	Author(s) of publication, comments Автор(ы) публикации, комментарии
<i>Dendarus armeniacus</i> Baudi di Selve, 1876	occurs in Turkey, Armenia, Iran and Afghanistan / встречается в Турции, Армении, Иране, Афганистане	only NE Iran and Turkmenistan according to current interpretation [Medvedev, 1968: 110] / встречается только в Северо-Восточном Иране и Туркменистане согласно современной интерпретации [Medvedev, 1968: 110]	The species was described from Armen(ia) ross(ica) [Baudi, 1876]. The type locality is unknown. Probably the current interpretation of this species is erroneous. The study of syntypes is necessary for clarifying the situation / Вид был описан из Armen(ia) ross(ica) [Baudi, 1876]. Типовое местонахождение неизвестно. Возможно, современная интерпретация этого вида ошибочная. Для прояснения ситуации необходимо изучение синтипов
<i>Dendarus extensus</i> (Faldermann, 1837)	occurs in Armenia, Iran and Turkmenistan / встречается в Армении, Иране и Туркменистане	occurs in Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan (Nakhichevan AR) and Turkey (Artvin Prov.) / встречается в Грузии, Армении, Азербайджане (Нахичеванская АР) и Турции (Артвин)	This species was erroneously listed for Iran and Turkmenistan [Gebien, 1938; Löbl et al., 2008]. Later it was excluded from their faunas by Abdurakhmanov and Nabozhenko [2011], but this correction was omitted in the new edition of the Catalogue [Iwan et al., 2020] and <i>D. extensus</i> was again erroneously indicated for Iran and Turkmenistan, but not for Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey / Этот вид был ошибочно указан для Ирана и Туркменистана [Gebien, 1938; Löbl et al., 2008]. Позже он был исключен из чек-листов этих стран Абдурахмановым и Набоженко [2011], но это исправление было упущено в новой редакции каталога, и <i>D. extensus</i> был снова ошибочно указан для Ирана и Туркменистана, но не для Грузии, Азербайджана и Турции
<i>Dendarus foveolatus</i> Seidlitz, 1893	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent in Armenia / отсутствует в Армении	The species occurs in Turkey [Medvedev, 1968: 99] and absent on the Caucasus [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011: 313]. The records from Armenia are based on the label of the syntypes (HNHM) "Armenien Erzurum Reitter" (now Turkey) / Вид встречается в Турции [Medvedev, 1968: 99] и отсутствует на Кавказе [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011: 313]. Указание для Армении основано на синтипах (HNHM) с этикеткой "Armenien Erzurum Reitter" (ныне Турция)
<i>Dendarus punctatus</i> Audinet-Serville, 1825	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent on the Caucasus / отсутствует на Кавказе	This species is reliably known only from steppes of the European part of Russia and the Ukraine. Records for Turkey and Armenia are erroneous and belongs to another species [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011: 229] / Этот вид на самом деле известен только из степей европейской части России и Украины. Указания для Турции и Армении ошибочны и относятся к другим видам [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011: 229]
<i>Dendarus simplex</i> Seidlitz, 1893	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent on the Caucasus / отсутствует на Кавказе	The species occurs in Turkey, Syria, Iraq and Iran according to Medvedev [1968: 108]. Records for Armenia are based on the original description ("Armenia?" as Seidlitz [1895] wrote) and specimens from modern Van Province of Turkey [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011: 313] / Вид встречается в Турции, Сирии, Ираке и Иране согласно Медведеву [1968: 108]. Находки для Армении основаны на оригинальном описании («Armenia?», как указано у Зайдлица Seidlitz [1895]) и экземплярах из современной турецкой провинции Ван

Table 1 (completion).
Таблица 1 (окончание).

Species or nomenclatural act / Вид или номенклатурный акт	In Catalogue В каталоге	Correction Исправление	Author(s) of publication, comments Автор(ы) публикации, комментарии
<i>Platynosum collare</i> Motschulsky, 1839	occurs in Armenia / встречается в Армении	absent in Armenia / отсутствует в Армении	The species is known only from the type locality: Ordubad (Nakhichevan AR, Azerbaijan) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011: 246] / Вид известен только из типового местонахождения: Ордубад (Нахичевань, Азербайджан) [Abdurakhmanov, Nabozhenko, 2011: 246]

pest of cereals as many other species of this genus [Halstead, 1967]. However, forests are absent in the Arpi in Armenia, and this record is probably the first registered invasion of this species to synanthropic habitats.

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